

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

New supply chain modeling in GLOBIOM

Deliverable 6.2

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the objectives of the CLEVER project is to improve and mobilize modelling tools to explore the effectiveness of innovative international trade and supply chain governance interventions on non-food biomass supply chains and biodiversity. This modelling component relies on the GLOBIOM land use model, which projects the dynamics of most important agricultural and forestry supply chains and their impacts on natural resources from the year 2000 into the future with a decadal time step (up to 2050 or even 2100).

As compared to other forward-looking dynamic supply chains modelling tools, this model has a relatively broad and yet detailed modelling of supply chains, covering globally the consumer demand for final products, trade and the supply of products at the scale of 59 market regions and for more than 50 products. The modelling of each agricultural and forestry production activities and related land and water use is done at subnational scale, with a multiple crop, livestock and forestry management intensities and a detailed land cover and land use change representation. A recent extension was allowed to cover blue food supply chains, i.e., fish and seafood. The modelling rests on a large number of datasets of various sources (e.g., from country-level or regional-level price elasticities and official statistics, to high spatial resolution datasets such remote sensing-based land cover products and biophysical model outputs). The standard version of the model balances across several priorities (e.g., high level of detail in modelled variables, use globally available data products, sufficiently low computation time) and is continuously updated as new datasets and methods become available, and specific modelling goals are pursued.

The planned model and scenario applications in CLEVER focus on the nexus of trade, supply chain governance and biodiversity impacts for three specific supply chains: soy – with a particular interest in Brazil and the EU – , forest biomass – with a particular interest in Brazil and the EU – , and aquaculture and aquafeed (globally). In order to improve the underlying GLOBIOM modelling framework for this, a number of activities are undertaken in Workpackage 6. This deliverable reports on the supply chain modelling improvements (Task 6.2), with explicit integration of the outputs of other tasks in WP6 such as new biophysical modelling outputs (Task 6.1), and improved biodiversity modelling methods and data (Task 6.3).

The deliverable is organized in three main sections. In the INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES section, we provide for each supply chain more background on the supply chain and its link to biodiversity, planned scenario and model applications, and a synthetic description of the model improvement objectives. Then, the METHODS section provides more detailed information on the status quo in the standard model version, the methods and data sources employed for improving the model, and the scenarios used to illustrate the model improvements. The ILLUSTRATIVE PROJECTIONS AND DISCUSSION section then analyses for each supply chain the projections of the improved model version for the illustrative scenario, before discussing achievements and potential further improvements within further Workpackage 6 and Workpackage 7 activities.

The modelling developments allowed significant improvements for each of the three focus supply chains, with potential for additional improvements within CLEVER. The latter are also

informed by the feedback received from stakeholders during a stakeholder workshop for two out of the three supply chains (forest and aquaculture & aquafeed), while such a workshop is planned to occur at a later date for soy supply chains.

Soy supply chains

Achievements: several features were introduced to better model oilseed market dynamics, subnational scale production patterns in Brazil and related biodiversity impacts. Among other, these made use of new biophysical data for soy production systems in Brazil described in CLEVER deliverable D6.1 and updated biodiversity impact quantification methods described in CLEVER deliverable D6.3. The illustrative projections demonstrated that the model improvements allowed partially capturing recent trends in both international trade in soy-based secondary products and Brazil soy harvested areas for single and multicropping systems at Federal State level, and quantifying related biodiversity impacts. The projections also highlighted the importance for trends to 2050 of relative differences in the future developments in vegetal oil and animal feed demands, substitutions between individual oilseed market products in those demands. Unless the world embark upon a sustainable path (SSP1 scenario), pressures on biodiversity will increase in the future, and with potentially shifting pressures from cropland expansion across major biomes of Brazil.

Directions for future work: as part of Workpackage 6 model improvements to better model value chains at actor level (Task 6.5) and Workpackage 7 scenario developments (Tasks 6.2 and Task 6.3), additional adjustments to model parameters may be useful to better match historical trends, and additional developments will be needed to parameterize the recent impact and/or potential future developments specific policies in Brazil (e.g., Soy Moratorium and Forest Code) and along international supply chains (e.g., EU-MERCOSUR, EUDR). This will include a parameterization of trade and land use costs to match estimated impacts of specific policies (see for example D3.2 for estimates of trade impacts from EUDR). The efforts to integrate novel biodiversity impact metrics will be finalized by using for Brazil the novel characterization factors for land stress impacts generated by CLEVER partners in WP2 and Task 6.3, next to the LC-IMPACT characterization factors used in this deliverable.

Forest supply chains

Achievements: an in-depth revision of the modelling of the forest management was conducted to better represent the gradient in forest management intensity and capture the use of forest plantations for roundwood production. Additional improvements were made to better model final demand sectors and recycling and re-use possibilities, as well as biodiversity impacts. This also made use of new biophysical data for forest plantations globally (CLEVER deliverable D6.1) and updated biodiversity impact quantification methods (CLEVER deliverable D6.3). For the latter, indicators based on LC_IMPACT were updated to a more recent reference to allow differentiating impacts across forest management classes: as they do not consider forestry impacts, the novel characterization factors generated through WP32 and WP6 could not be integrated for forest supply chains. The illustrative model projections allowed to demonstrate the ability of the improved model version to capture changes in forest management. They also highlighted the role of forest plantations, in particular in Latin America and Asia, as an option to

meet future biomass demand, but also potentially a risk of leakage of biodiversity impacts from forest areas to non-forested natural ecosystems via a displacement of agricultural activities.

Directions for future work: As part of Workpackage 6 model improvements to better model value chains at actor level (Task 6.5) and Workpackage 7 scenario developments (Tasks 6.2 and Task 6.3), additional developments would be useful to better capture the role of abandoned agricultural land and the fate of biodiversity in it, carbon stock vs biodiversity trade offs (e.g., age class dynamics to assess forest carbon stocks). It would also be useful to refine forest plantations in Brazil, and parameterize scenarios for restoration and conservation policy ambitions in the EU (e.g., EU Biodiversity Strategy) and in Brazil (e.g., Forest Code).

Aquaculture and aquafeed supply chains

Achievements: we documented the GLOBIOM fish module, improved and documented the parameterization of a business-as-usual future scenario for blue food demand and aquaculture production, and included an estimate of on-farm aquaculture nutrient losses and terrestrial biodiversity impacts from the cultivation of crop-based aquafeeds. This also made use of updated biodiversity impact quantification methods (CLEVER deliverable D6.3). The illustrative projections allowed demonstrating that the model is able to capture recent historical trends, and the expected future increase in future blue food demand, the growing role of aquaculture to meet this demand (in particular for freshwater products), and the potential impacts the related crop-based aquafeed could have on terrestrial biodiversity. Even though potentially modest, the latter involve teleconnections across regions via trade. It also demonstrated the role of recent and future increases in feed conversion efficiency and fish-based vs. crop-based aquafeed substitutions.

Directions for future work: As part of Workpackage 6 model improvements to better model value chains at actor level (Task 6.5) and Workpackage 7 scenario developments (Tasks 6.2 and Task 6.3), additional developments would be useful to refine some key technical assumptions (e.g., maximum rate of fish oil substitution), and to picture alternative scenarios concerning the demand (e.g., towards farmed bivalves), marine catch levels (e.g., towards sustainable levels), and more efficient and integrated aquaculture production systems (e.g., including based on using macro-algae as aquafeed). In addition, an additional benchmark with blue food demand and supply maintained constant to 2020 levels might useful to isolate the impact of blue food within the broader land use sector developments. The efforts to integrate novel biodiversity impact metrics will be finalized by using for Brazil the novel characterization factors for land stress impacts generated by CLEVER partners in WP2 and Task 6.3, next to the LC-IMPACT characterization factors used in this deliverable.

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Soy supply chains

Soy is the fourth most important crop in terms of global harvested area, used predominantly as animal feed and vegetal oil, and one of the most traded commodities globally (De Maria et al. 2020). Significant developments in the oilseed markets that occurred in the past two decades, such as a large rise in animal feed and vegetable oil demand and international trade in soy and oil palm, are expected to continue but slowdown in the coming decade (OECD and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2024). While the USA remains a large producer since the second half of the 20th century, the sustained increases in global soy production and trade in recent decades also relied on a rapid development of soy production in other countries such as Brazil, which have been linked to deforestation and biodiversity losses through increases in cropland extent, partially dampened by supply chain regulation efforts (Green et al. 2019). The cropland expansion related to the development of soy production systems was also mitigated by a large increase in the productivity of soy production systems, through genetic improvements and the adoption of novel production systems such as soy-corn double cropping (Abrahão and Costa 2018; Xu et al. 2021). The impact of future demand for soy on biodiversity in the coming decades will depend on the interplay between these various factors.

In the WP7 of the CLEVER project, we set out to use the GLOBIOM land use model with new scenarios in order to analyse the potential future evolution of soy trade, production, related socio-economic and environmental impacts, and the role of various supply chain and trade policy interventions in regulating those, with a focus on Brazil-EU soy supply chains. To support this objective, the task 6.2 of CLEVER aims to improve the representation of this supply chain in the GLOBIOM global land use model, detailed in this deliverable. The main objectives for these improvements are the following:

- Improve the modelling of dynamics in demand, processing and trade in secondary products for oilseed crops at global scale. The current version of the model includes some representation of the processing of crops (including soy, but also rapeseed, oil palm, corn, wheat) to produce biofuels, as well as the use of by-products (such as soy meal) to feed livestock. However, the trade in secondary products is often ignored, several stages of the supply chains are modelled in primary products equivalents, and possibilities for substitutions between products in the demands are not explicitly represented beyond a rigid substitution in animal feed of oilseed and cereal crops by protein cakes. The goal is to explicitly model at regional level the demand for secondary products (oils and cakes), possible substitutions between various vegetable oils (in food and other uses demand) or protein meals (in feed demand), the trade for secondary products (oils and cakes), and the crushing of various oil crops. This development is expected to improve the realism of the future projections, and will leverage available datasets from various sources and previous efforts at modelling vegetal oil markets in the iLUC version of the model (H. Valin et al. 2015).
- Improve the modelling of the dynamics of soy production systems in Brazil. In the current version of the model, these dynamics are already represented but rely on the default parameterization of the model. The latter is based on globally available data

sources, a regional-scale representation of multi-cropping without cropping system or subnational detail, and a relatively coarse spatial resolution for the modelling of crop production and land use decisions. The goal is to increase the spatial resolution at which the crop production and land use decisions are modelled, substitute existing datasets that characterize the initial area and yield of soy production systems by tailored datasets (e.g., official Brazil agricultural statistics at municipality level, estimates from the EPIC biophysical model produced in D6.1), and fine-tune the representation of multi-cropping to better represent soy-corn production systems. This is expected to improve the realism of projected future dynamics of soy production systems, will leverage novel datasets generated in CLEVER (e.g., EPIC biophysical model developed in CLEVER task 6.1) and previous work with the Brazil version of the model (e.g., Soterroni et al. 2018; 2019).

- Improve the estimates of biodiversity impacts. The standard biodiversity indicators in GLOBIOM include the Fraction of Remaining Species (based on a countryside Species Area Relationship model) and the Biodiversity Intactness Index (based on the PREDICTS database and model). These indicators do not include other impacts than land use (such as climate change) or ecosystems other than terrestrial ecosystems (such as freshwater ecosystems, subject to water stress, climate change and eutrophication impacts). To do so, we will integrate the developments from Task 6.3 to connect GLOBIOM to Life Cycle Impact Assessment methods, as described in CLEVER Deliverable D6.3.

We illustrate the improvements by comparing a baseline projection of oilseed markets globally and soy production in Brazil over 2000-2030 with statistics and reference projections, and analyse projections from simple scenarios about future trends over 2030-2050.

Forest supply chains

Forest plantations (or plantation forests) are intensively managed planted forests, including short rotation plantations for wood production, and currently represent 3% of the world forest area for 30% of global industrial roundwood production (FAO 2020). They could provide a play a dominant role in meeting high biomass demands associated with climate neutrality strategies (Mishra et al. 2022). Moreover, a considerable share of fuelwood is currently sourced from plantations in countries like Brazil (ABRAF 2011). Forest plantations expansion has been historically driven by wood demands and have also occupied large areas of natural forest areas, with impacts on forest carbon and biodiversity (Ramos, Nuvoloni, and Lopes 2022). Nowadays, they are also considered a tool for restoring land and being part of solutions to increase biomass-climate and biodiversity (Campoe, Stape, and Mendes 2010). An example of this nexus is shown in the Forest Code in Brazil, where plantations are considered for a certain extent also in the restoration options for degraded land.

The GLOBIOM global land use model has an explicit representation of energy crops plantations grown outside the forest area for energy production (Havlík et al. 2011) and more recently in silvopastoral systems (Frank et al. 2024). However, forest plantations established within or outside the current forest area were only implicitly included in natural and seminatural forest areas, while a more explicit representation was not possible due to lack of data to calibrate initial and recent forest plantations area. Recently, new global datasets were provided by FAO that allows to calibrate and model forest plantations for historical periods 2000-2020 (FAO 2020), together with aligned projections. However, assumptions on land-use suitability for expansion of plantations within or outside the current forest area remain very uncertain, given ecological impacts of their highly intensive cultivation schemes compared to management of natural and seminatural forests.

Apart from forest plantations, at least two other dimensions of forest supply chains are important the biomass-climate-biodiversity nexus. First, several dimensions of the forest area management intensity (e.g., whether the forest is primary or not, tree species, and management type) have a key impact on the biomass and biodiversity dynamics within forests (Gusti et al. 2020; Chaudhary et al. 2016), and are an increasing focus of conservation and restoration policies. For example, the EU Biodiversity strategy and the EU Forest Strategy are targeting an increase uptake of close-to-nature forest management (European Commission 2020; 2021). In the standard version of the GLOBIOM model, forests already present in the year 2000 can only vary between two types of management (managed – with wood extraction – or unmanaged – without wood extraction), which limits the capacity of the model to inform on biomass-climate-biodiversity nexus interactions.

Several aspects of the forest wood supply chain stages downstream from harvest (e.g., processing, final demand) have a key impact on the material demand required to fulfil various types of final demands and are an increasing focus of circular economy policies. For example, an increased the recycling and reuse of wood products could allow decreasing the pressure of biomass on forest resources, and the substitution of carbon-intensive material by biomass products with long lifetime could contribute to climate mitigation, with however trade-offs across various types of demand over different time horizons (Bais-Moleman et al. 2018; Brunet-

Navarro et al. 2021). In the standard version of GLOBIOM, wood processing chains are already relatively detailed with demand being specified for semi-finished products (chemical pulp, mechanical pulp, dissolving pulp, sawnwood, plywood, fiberboard), but a finer representation in terms of final demand sectors would enable a better representation of circular economy measures.

Given the challenge of assessing the socioeconomic and environmental impacts of global supply chains for forest biomass, it is of key importance to distinguish wood sourced from areas classified as natural or seminatural forests compared to wood sourced from plantations, to better represent the management of natural and seminatural forests, and to better represent the diversity of forest sector end uses. To do so, in CLEVER task 6.2 we focused on the following enhancements to the GLOBIOM model:

- Include a representation of “forest plantations for roundwood production” in GLOBIOM, as a separate land use/forest management option that can be allocated within existing forest land or as conversion of agricultural land. Energy wood plantations outside forest land were kept in the model as a separate land use category permitted to expand only on agricultural land. The roundwood plantations were differentiated between coniferous and non-coniferous species. The biophysical data (increments, carbon-stocks) for roundwood plantations was based on estimates from the i3PGMIX process-based vegetation model, which was also used to replace the biophysical data for energy plantations previously based on (Aoki 2011). Historical plantations area development is calibrated to match (FAO 2020) country level database (for the period 2000-2020), and downscaled to GLOBIOM grid level using a global forest management map (Lesiv et al. 2022). This calibration enabled the inclusion of roundwood plantations within forest area according to historical statistics.
- Increase the level of detail with which the management of natural and semi-natural forests (i.e., forests other than forest plantations) is represented, and revisiting the dynamics of forest area in relation to other land uses (afforestation/deforestation/plantations expansion in other land uses). This includes revising the unmanaged forest class into three classes and the managed forest class into six classes, based on assumptions about protection, species mix, rotation time, and harvest intensity, and datasets such as the World Database on Protected Areas, FAO’s Forest Resource Assessment, a global map of forest management (Lesiv et al. 2022), a global forestry cost database (Di Fulvio et al. 2016) and biophysical parameter estimates from the G4M global forestry model (Gusti and Kindermann 2011).
- Improve the estimation of biodiversity impacts from forest plantations as well as natural and semi-natural products. To that end, the LC-IMPACT approach presented in D6.3 for land occupation and land transformation impacts on terrestrial ecosystems was adjusted for the new forest plantation and forest management classes, based on the characterization factors from (Scherer et al. 2023).
- Improve the forest product supply chain representation, with a refined set of primary products, processing activities, and a modeling of final demand sectors. The primary products were split between coniferous and non-coniferous tree species, with a region-specific link between the new forest plantation and natural and semi-natural forest management classes and the type of primary product supplied. The historical separation of coniferous vs non-coniferous products was calibrated on FAOSTAT. An additional

processing step, from semi-finished products (Sawnwood, Plywood, Fiberboard, Chemical pulp, Mechanical pulp, Dissolving pulp, Other fiber-pulp) to final end use sector aggregated products (Construction, Furniture, Woodpacking, Paperboards, Printing-writing paper, Newsprint paper, Textiles) was added, and the demand was modelled for final end use sector aggregated products (instead of semi-finished products). Additional processes relating to the recycling of final products were added.

We illustrate the improvements by analysing projections from simple scenarios about future trends in biomass demand and forest management, centred on the role of forest plantations in meeting future demand.

Aquaculture and aquafeeds

The demand of aquatic food products is expected to increase in the coming decades, as result of increasing population and shifting incomes (Naylor et al. 2021), as well as efforts to reduce the environmental impact of food consumption (Halpern et al. 2022). As marine catch stagnates and may already be beyond sustainable potentials, a large share of the future aquatic food demand increase is expected to be met by aquaculture (FAO 2018). Yet, about half of today's total aquaculture requires feed inputs that relied traditionally on fish meal and fish oil aquafeeds produced from the reduction of pelagic fish catch, and margins to increase the supply of traditional aquafeeds may be limited by the ecological impacts of the fish reduction sector (Froehlich, Jacobsen, et al. 2018). While improvements in aquaculture feed conversion efficiencies (Gephart et al. 2021) or the uptake of novel aquafeeds (Cottrell et al. 2020) may contribute to alleviating such a pressure, crop-based aquafeed are increasingly being used as an alternative to traditional aquafeeds (Tacon and Metian 2015). Future scenarios about dietary changes, food demand and aquaculture and aquafeed developments indicate potentially important land use implications (Froehlich, Runge, et al. 2018). Blue food demand and crop aquafeeds are therefore considered as one of the main interactions between land and sea supply chains (Cottrell et al. 2018), which remain poorly captured by integrated modelling tools and assessments.

The GLOBIOM global land use model has recently been extended to cover key blue food supply chains, including an endogenous representation of demand, trade and production for fish products (Spillias et al. 2025). The fish production covers both the catch from marine fisheries and the supply from aquaculture production systems, these two forms of production being connected through the fish reduction sector (processing marine catch into fish meal and fish oil, used as aquaculture feed), the aquaculture sector is connected to the GLOBIOM crop sector through crop aquafeed, while the demand for blue food final products is explicitly modelled.

In the WP7 of the CLEVER project, we will use this augmented GLOBIOM version with new scenarios in order to analyse the potential future evolution of blue food demand and supply (including aquaculture production and fish reduction), the impact of alternative aquaculture feeding strategies, and potential impacts on land-related sustainability dimensions. To support this objective, the task 6.2 of CLEVER consists of documentation efforts and selected model developments with the following objectives:

- Improve the documentation of this model version and the parameterization of a business-as-usual future scenario. While a more detailed description is being prepared as part of an upcoming research article, we provide here a basic description of the different components of the fish module, as well as key equations and data sources, and assumptions for a business-as-usual future scenario. Additional equations were introduced to stabilize the regional patterns of aquaculture supply beyond 2020.
- Complement the existing model with a quantification of biodiversity impacts associated with the production of crop aquafeeds (based on the developments from task 6.3).
- Complement the existing model with a quantification of waste losses within aquaculture production systems.

We illustrate the improvements by analysing projections from simple scenarios about future trends in fish product demand and aquaculture feeding practices.

METHODS

Soy supply chains

Status-quo

Oilseed crops supply chains

The current version of GLOBIOM models most products in primary equivalents and end uses categorized as food, biofuel, animal feed, or other demand. An exception is the processing of crops (including soy, rapeseed, oil palm, corn, and wheat) for biofuel production, as well as the use of protein cakes as livestock feed. Protein cakes are co-products of primary crop processing in biofuel supply chains. For example soya bean is first crushed into soy oil (with soy protein cake as a co-product), which is further processed into biodiesel. However, vegetable oil are not represent as specific products with dedicated crushing and trade, and other uses of vegetable oils (e.g., food or industrial use) are implicitly included in the rest of soy supply chain-related final demand in primary crop-equivalent, with no related protein cake co-production, use or trade. Neither possible substitutions between vegetable oils in the demand for food or other (e.g., industrial) uses, or between protein cakes in livestock feed are accounted for. Finally, the trade in secondary products such as oils and protein cakes are not accounted for. This simplified representation of oilseed crop supply chains limits the accuracy and details in the modelling of supply chains and environmental impacts from oilseed crops, including soya and oil palm. In CLEVER, to improve the realism of the future projections we seek to enhance the representation of the oilseed crop supply chains within GLOBIOM by explicitly modelling:

- the demand for secondary products (oils and cakes),
- the crushing of various oil crops into oils and cakes,
- the trade for secondary products (oils and cakes),
- possible substitutions between individual protein meals in feed,
- possible substitutions between individual vegetable oils in food and other use,

Soy production systems in Brazil

In the standard version of GLOBIOM, as described in the GLOBIOM documentation (IBF-IIASA 2023), several factors may limit the accuracy in the modelling of soy production systems in Brazil, and their dynamics. Firstly, the model variables (e.g., cropland extent, conversion of other land uses to cropland, harvested area of different crops) and parameters (e.g., crop yields) associated to crop production systems are modelled at subnational resolution with a relatively coarse spatial resolution, defined by the intersection of 120 arcmin grid cells – ca 200 by 200 km at the equator – with country boundaries. Such a spatial resolution may be limited when for example assessing the impacts of land use and land use change on ecosystems and biodiversity.

Secondly, the predefined typology of production systems differentiates the harvested area of single crops by four input intensity levels (subsistence, rainfed low and high input, irrigated high input) with multiple cropping only considered as a country-level, crop-specific multipliers relating physical to harvested areas. This owes to the nature of the datasets available with global coverage when it comes to crop production systems for the year 2000, but limits the capacity of

the model to account for the rise of key production systems for Brazil soy production, such as soya-corn double cropping.

Moreover, all the data used to initialize and calibrate the model for the year 2000 in terms of land cover, land use, animal- and livestock production system-specific numbers, as well as crop- and crop production-system physical and harvested areas is based on data sources with global coverage, such as remote sensing-based global land cover and use maps (e.g., GLC2000, citation), and global crop systems map (e.g., SPAM, citation). At the scale of individual countries, and in particular for a data-rich country such as Brazil, this may not be as accurate as locally available datasets.

At last, the parameters used in equations defining the inertia of production system dynamics (e.g., maximum rate of increase in harvested area per time step) are usually uniform at the country level, which may limit the capacity to reproduce subnational trends in the development of production systems over time.

In CLEVER, we seek to enhance the representation of soy production systems and land use dynamics in Brazil by enriching the standard model version with features that were developed in Brazil-tailored version of the model co-developed by collaborators from the Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas Espaciais (INPE), the Instituto de Pesquisa Economica Aplicada (IPEA) and IIASA (Câmara et al. 2015; Soterroni et al. 2018):

- Introducing a new type of crop production system in Brazil, consisting of soya-corn double cropping
- Substituting global data sources on initial land cover, land use, crop-specific harvested and physical area and livestock numbers for the year 2000
- Adjusting the parameters governing the development of single soy and soya-corn double cropping across the various federal states and biomes of Brazil

Improved modelling of vegetal oil supply chains

Refined markets, supply chains and products

To better represent the dynamics of oilseed crop and oil palm supply chains, we followed the approach already developed for version of the model used to estimate the indirect land use change effects of various biofuels (H. Valin et al. 2015). For key oilseed crops represented in the model (soy, rapeseed, sunflower) and for oil palm, we substituted in the standard version of the model the representation of a single market (e.g., e.g., parameters, variables and equations associated to supply, demand, processing, trade) for a single primary product-equivalent product (e.g., soya) by markets for several primary and secondary products (e.g., soya bean, soya oil and soil cake). In the standard version a crop product-to-biofuel processing stage was already represented: as illustrated in Figure 1 and Table 1, in the improved model version an additional crushing processing stage has been introduced, together with its outputs products (oil and protein cake). While the demand for bioenergy was already specified as dedicated bioenergy final products, for other uses (food, feed and other uses) the final demand was specified for the secondary products, rather than for the primary product, and all connections to other model components (e.g., bioenergy refinery, food and other use, feed) were adjusted.

Figure 1 - Schematic overview of supply chains in GLOBIOM and role of processing industries (source: Valin et al., 2015)

Table 1 - Comparison of products and market stages explicitly modelled before and after model improvements.

Product	Supply	Food & other use	Feed	Bioenergy	Crushing	Trade
<i>Standard version</i>						
Rape (rapeseed, primary prod. equ.)	x(*)	X	x	x	x	x
Sunf (sunflower, primary prod. equ.)	x(*)	X	x	x	x	x
Soya (soy, primary prod. equ.)	x(*)	X	x	x	x	x
OPAL (oil palm, primary prod. equ.)	x(*)	X	x	x	x	x
<i>Improved version</i>						
Rape (rapeseed, crop)	x(*)	X	x	-	x	x
RapO (rapeseed, oil)	x(#)	X	-	x	-	x
RapC (rapeseed, protein meal)	x(#)	-	x	-	-	x
Sunf (sunflower, crop)	x(*)	X	x	-	x	x
RapO (rapeseed, oil)	x(#)	x	-	x	-	x
RapC (rapeseed, protein meal)	x(#)	-	x	-	-	x
Soya (soy, crop)	x	x	x	-	x	x
SoyO (rapeseed, oil)	x(#)	x	-	x	-	x
SoyC (rapeseed, protein meal)	x(#)	-	x	-	-	x
OPAL (oil palm, primary prod. equ.)	x	x	x	-	x	-
PlmO (palm oil & palm kernel oil)	x(#)	x	-	x	-	x
PlmN (palm kernel & palm kernel cake)	x(#)	x	-	-	-	x

(*) through harvest; (#) through crushing

As detailed in Table 1, for the 3 main oilseed crops (soy, rapeseed, sunflower) the new model version distinguishes vegetal oils (used for biofuel, food and other uses) from protein meals (used for feed, food and other uses) secondary products, which corresponds to a traditional representation of oilseed crop processing chains. The oil palm fruit was assumed not to be traded, as it needs to be crushed rapidly following the harvest and is predominantly not traded. However, it should be noted that for the oil palm supply chains, some additional simplifications were made. A traditional representation of this supply chain would include not only the crushing of oil palm fruits to generate palm oil and palm kernel, but also the crushing of palm kernels into palm kernel oil – used as a vegetable oil, for food and other uses – and palm kernel cakes – used as food and other uses, but also livestock feed. To limit the number of processing steps, we decided to omit the palm kernel crushing and model only two products: PlmO (consisting of both palm oil and palm kernel oil) and PlmN (consisting of palm kernel and palm kernel cakes). The demand for PlmO is thus larger than the pure oil palm demand (as it also includes palm kernel oil), the processing of OPAL to PlmO is more effective than the pure processing of oil palm to palm oil (as it also includes palm kernel oil generated from further crushing the palm kernel into palm kernel oil), and the final demand of PlmN is higher than that of pure palm kernel (as it includes the demand for palm kernel cake). As it represents a relatively low share of total oil palm end use and also a relatively low share of total feed input, we decided to omit the use of palm kernel cakes as livestock feed (there is therefore no feed use modelled for PlmN).

Modelling of crushing process

In addition to the addition of the new secondary product, a crushing process was introduced in the model. Detailed processing data about input-output coefficients and processing costs has been incorporated, based on FAOSTAT data and additional data collected in the iLUC version of the GLOBIOM model (H. Valin et al. 2015). As mentioned in the next section, the processing costs are also adjusted through the trade cost calibration procedure.

To stabilize the evolution of the crushing capacity at regional level, a new equation was introduced to limit the possible decrease in crushing quantity from one time to another. It was assumed that crushing of individual crops (OPAL, Rape, Soya, Sunf) cannot decrease by less than 80% in a 10-year time step. This does not limit upward changes in crushing capacity.

Finally, gains in conversion efficiency have been integrated into the model for oil palm supply chains, with an increase from 2000 to 2010 (resp. 2020) in the quantity of PlmO produced from 1 ton of OPAL by 2.5 % (resp. 5%) for Malaysia and 13% (resp. 17.5%) in Indonesia.

Changes to trade cost data and calibration

The improved representation did not require any change in the main equations governing trade in the model, but necessitated to re-process the original data used to specify and calibrate trade costs in order to change the product resolution. The BACI bilateral trade data (Gaulier and Zignago 2010) is available with a finer disaggregation level than represented in GLOBIOM, and bilateral trade data could be estimated for all products listed as traded for the improved version of the model in Table 1. Similarly, tariff data could be estimated from the MACMAP database (Bouët et al. 2004), and FAOSTAT production, price, exports, imports, consumption, and stock for all these products. The calibration of trade for these products followed the same procedure than for all products in the standard version of the model, except that the crushing processing costs are also adjusted together with trade costs.

Modeling of vegetal oil demand and substitution between individual oils

Following the iLUC version of the GLOBIOM model (Valin et al 2015), the vegetables oils produced from crushing (RapO, SoyO, SunO, PlmO) were linked to bioenergy refinery processing (with processing coefficients adjusted), and to newly estimated demand functions for food and other uses. These new demand functions have a similar formulation to that of other products in GLOBIOM, as constant price elasticity demand functions. The reference price and quantity values are estimated from based on FAOSTAT data on price and quantities for the year 2000, the price elasticity is derived from the USDA price elasticity database (Muhammad et al. 2011), and the reference quantity is adjusted according to FAOSTAT data for 2010, and to SSP projections (Hugo Valin et al. 2014) derived from historical relationships between GDP, income level and past demand levels for the following time steps (e.g., 2020, 2030, 2040, 2050). To do so, the FAOSTAT data for prices and quantities was re-estimated without aggregating secondary products into primary products. For price elasticity, the vegetable oils are linked to the 'Fat and oils' USDA product category, while PlmN was linked to the 'Fruits & vegetables' USDA product category.

However, at the difference of the standard version, we follow the iLUC version of the model and consider the possibility of substitution between vegetable oils in the food and other use demand. This allows the modelled consumption of total vegetable oil and individual oils to react to changes in the price of other individual oils, as affected by other demands in the supply chain (e.g., processing of oil for biofuel, or demand of cakes for animal feed), or constraints on the supply and trade of specific primary or secondary products. To do so, the demand for final food and other use vegetable oil products is not modeled for separate individual oil products (SoyO, SunO, RapO, PlmO), but instead for a single product bundle (VegOil). An additional equation equates the supply of the bundle VegOil supplied to the sum of a 'bundle' oil term (combining all individual oils in fixed proportions, DQuantity_Mix), and an 'individual' oil term (individual oils, DQuantity_Subs) subject to a linearized quadratic cost. The share of individual oils in VegOil is recursively adjusted at each time step, allowing the model to dynamically adjust to changing market conditions.

Modeling of animal feed demand and substitution between individual protein cakes and other feed items

The standard version of the model (IBF-IIASA 2023) has a detailed representation of livestock feed, including various grain concentrate items (from crops) as well as roughage feed (from pastures) in fixed proportions that depend on each livestock and livestock production system (Havlík et al. 2014). The various grain concentrate items can correspond to single crops (e.g., soya) or groups of crops (e.g., other oilseed crops, that includes rapeseed, sunflower, oil palm, groundnut and cotton). For grain concentrate items corresponding to groups of crops, the share of various constituting crops is estimated in the year 2000 and then assumed constant. The model also includes the possibility to substitute the crop feed used as grain concentrates by biofuel production co-products (e.g., dry distiller grains and oilseed protein cakes), in fixed proportions defined by displacement ratios (e.g., 1 ton of rapeseed protein cake replaces 0.66 ton of soya crop feed and 0.26 ton of corn crop feed).

Following the iLUC version of the model (Valin et al 2015), in the improved version for this deliverable we made additional modifications to the modeling of feed requirements for grain concentrates:

- We adjusted the mapping between grain concentrate items and oilseed and palm products to account for the split between primary and secondary products. The soy oil was mapped to the soy grain concentrate item (together with the primary soy crop) while other oils (RapO, SunO, PlmO) were mapped to the other oilseed crops crop group, together with the primary oilseed crops except oil palm (e.g., Rape, Sunf). The cakes (RapC, SoyC, SunC) were added to a new grain concentrate item (protein cakes PrtC), together with other biofuel processing co-products (wheat and corn dry distiller grains).
- Similar to the standard version, the share of various oils and primary crops in concentrate grain items is estimated in the year 2000, and assumed constant in the following time step.
- To allow for a more flexible substitution between individual oil cakes and feed product used for grain concentrate items, we introduced the possibility adopt alternative feed rations that correspond to selected substitution strategies, based on the incorporation

of one protein cake to replace another one, with further adjustment to one cereal grain to maintain metabolizable energy (which associated with the livestock grain concentrate intake). A small linear cost is introduced to stabilize the adoption of alternative rations.

A final important development was to improve the evolution of the livestock feed requirements changes since the year 2000. The feed requirements in the model are differentiated per animal and livestock production system, based on a large data compilation effort (Havlík et al. 2014), and the projected evolution of the livestock numbers per animal and system allows to capture some of the observed trends in feed input. However, in particular for monogastric animals (pigs, poultry), the modelling approach does not capture the evolution of changes feed practices in some countries (such as the large increase in soy feed requirements from countries like China), especially now that the protein cakes have been added as a new grain concentrate item whose requirements per animal and livestock production system is assumed unchanged. We therefore adjusted the animal feed requirements for pigs and poultry for urban systems in several countries, including a large substitution of crop-based grain concentrate items by protein cake-based grain concentrate in China phased over 2000-2030.

Improved modelling of soy production systems in Brazil

Update of initial land cover, land use, crop production and livestock production data

As part of a collaboration with INPE and IPEA, and described in detail in Camara et al 2015, a significant effort was done to update the data used for initializing the model for Brazil, in terms of land cover, land use, and crop and livestock production systems. In addition, we made use of the new simulations from the EPIC crop model for soy systems in Brazil, as described in CLEVER deliverable D6.1. Table 2 provides a summary of the different data components updated, and key data sources.

Table 2 - Key model input data updates and related data sources for Brazil

Model data input	Data source in standard GLOBIOM version (IBF-IIASA 2023)	Data source used for CLEVER update (reference land cover and land use map for Brazil in 2000, Câmara et al. 2015)
Land cover and land use (year 2000)	GEOBENE database (Skalský et al. 2008), based on GLC2000 remote sensing-based land cover map and SPAM cropland use map	IBGE vegetation map (IBGE 2012), and additional spatially explicit data for the Legal Amazon and Mata Atlantica biome.
Physical and Harvested area per crop and crop production system (year 2000)	SPAM dataset for the year 2000 (You and Wood 2006), harmonized to FAOSTAT at national level	IBGE Municipality Crop Production Survey (PAM), harmonized to FAOSTAT at national level
Crop yields and input use (year 2000)	Global outputs from the EPIC biophysical crop model	Updated global outputs from the EPIC biophysical crop model (with more extensive spatial coverage) for all crops and updated EPIC outputs for soy production systems in Brazil (CLEVER Deliverable D6.1)
Livestock numbers (year 2000)	International Livestock Research Institute/FAO production systems (Seré and Steinfeld 1996), Gridded livestock of the world (Robinson et al. 2011)	IBGE Municipality Livestock Production Survey (PPM), harmonized to FAOSTAT at national level
Grassland productivity (year 2000)	Multiple sources (Havlík et al. 2014)	Based on livestock requirements (livestock numbers from IBGE/PPM and feed requirements from Havlik et al 2014) and pasture area (based on IBGE/PPM and IBGE 2006 census data, and MODIS remote sensing data for the legal Amazon)

This data update was combined with another model improvement, increasing the spatial resolution within Brazil. Specifically, the spatial resolution at which land use and land use change variables are modelled was increased by a factor four: from an intersection of a 120 arcmin grid (roughly 200 by 200 km at the equator) with country boundaries to the intersection of 30 arcmin grid (roughly 50 by 50 km at the equator). All datasets were recompiled at this resolution, and the resolution of all related variables and parameters in the model was increased.

Altogether, these two developments will improve the model accuracy not only for the year 2000 but also subsequent model projections, through better calibration, a more accurate description

of available land resource for cropland and pasture expansion, and a higher resolution in land use and land use change projections.

Characterizing a new practice: soya-corn double cropping system

As a result of targeted soy crop genetic improvements, soy cultivation became feasible further North from the traditional growing region in Southern Brazil, and over the 2000-2020 period a double cropping system involving the cultivation of soybean (1st crop) followed by corn (2nd crop) in the same year has considerably developed (Abrahão and Costa 2018). This development is estimated to have contributed to a significant buffering of the land pressure associated with the rising demand for soy exports (Xu et al 2021), and is an important development to capture with the model. To better analyse soy supply chains, we included in the improved CLEVER model version the representation of soya-corn double cropping developed for the Brazil-zoomed version of the model (Soterroni et al. 2019).

This new crop management system has two harvests (for soy and corn) in a given year, and was modelled based on the following assumptions:

- The yields and fertilizer requirements were initialized with spatially-explicit outputs from the new EPIC simulations done in CLEVER Task 6.1 (see CLEVER Deliverable D6.1). Referring to D6.1 Table 4, soy yields for single crops are derived from the soy monocropping with s110 soy cultivar, no weed, residue retention, no mulching, no irrigation and conventional tillage (resp. soy cover cropping with s110 soy cultivar, millet intercropping, residue retention, mulching, no irrigation and minimal tillage) simulations for rainfed low input systems LI (resp. rainfed high input systems HI), and soy and corn yields and input requirements for the soy-corn double cropping system were derived from the soy-corn double cropping with s95 soy cultivar and c140 corn cultivar, no cover crop, minimal tillage, residue retention, mulching and no irrigation).
- Similar to the INPE model version, the production costs are initialized to 150% of the average soy production cost in the same grid cell.
- The double cropping system was assumed not to exist in the year 2000 (zero harvested area), and we relied on the IGBE/PAM dataset providing the split of corn harvested area by 1st corn vs 2nd corn at municipality level (from the year 2003 onwards) to parameterize the emergence of the crop in 2010. The 2010 starting condition of the model for the soya-corn double cropping system harvested area was updated to half of harvested area for 2nd corn reported by IGBE/PAM for 2020, and the harvested area of other soya and corn crop management systems were reduced accordingly. The harvested area for subsequent time steps is governed by the constraints on the expansion of crop and crop management systems present in a spatial unit in 2010.

Modifying equations and parameters governing crop expansion

To allow for a finer control of the subnational patterns in the expansion of soy harvested area and the extent to which it can expand over forests, the following modifications were performed:

- In the equation controlling for each crop in each subnational spatial unit (30 arcmin grid intersected with country boundaries for Brazil) the expansion of individual crops from one time step to another (MAXCROP_EQU), the maximum expansion rate parameter

- (MAXCROP_COEF) was made specific to each crop and subnational spatial unit (instead of country level value for each crop);
- The equation controlling for each crop management system in each subnational spatial unit (30 arcmin grid intersected with country boundaries for Brazil) the expansion of individual crop management systems (MAXCROPSYS_EQU) was made specific to different crop groups (soy, sugarcane, dry beans and rice, all other crops), and the maximum expansion rate parameter (MAXCROPSYS_COEF) was made specific to crop, crop management system, crop group and subnational spatial unit (instead of country level value for each crop and crop management system);
 - A new land use (SoyLnd) category was introduced, to differentiate cropland used to grow soya from other cropland, and possible land use transitions were adjusted in equations governing land use change (e.g., deforestation to cropland was split into deforestation to soy land vs deforestation to other natural land).

Initial values for relevant parameters are presented in Table 3, with higher values for sugarcane and soy over all Brazil, much higher values for soy in the Amazon biome, and slightly lower values for corn, beans and rice. These initial values were adjusted further to improve the match to historical developments over 2000-2020 for soy-corn systems (based on a sensitivity analysis, leading to higher values for key states like Mato Grosso), and reflect scenario assumptions after 2020. The specific modelling of land use conversions from/to land use for soybean allows for keeping track of direct land use changes related to soy expansion.

Table 3 - Initial values for key parameters in equations governing soy expansion in Brazil

Crop group	Values for MAXCROP_COEF and MAXCROPSYS_COEF (e.g., 1.5 means a maximum increase of 50% per time step)
soya (including soya-corn double cropping)	2 in all Brazil, slightly higher for Cerrado (2.5), and much higher in Amazon biome (8 for single soy, 4 for soy corn)
corn (excluding soya-corn double cropping)	1.15 in all Brazil
sugarcane	3.5 in all Brazil
beans and rice	1.15 in all Brazil
all other crops	1.5 everywhere in Brazil

In addition, and following initial developments from the Brazil-zoomed version of the model, the slope of the non-linear land use change cost function associated with conversion to cropland and pasture (from either forest, other natural vegetation, pasture or cropland) have been decreased by a factor 100 to allow a higher rate of agricultural land expansion.

Additional features for production patterns added to the model

Sugarcane is another important crop in Brazil, with a large development of domestic demand for bioenergy over 2000-2020, and dedicated policy instruments to regulate related cropland expansion, such as the agroecological zoning (AEZ) for sugarcane, implemented in 2009. The AEZ identifies favorable and unfavorable areas for cropland expansion to sugarcane (based on biophysical, hydrological and ecological considerations) and prevents expansion in the Amazon and the Pantanal biomes. In order to better control for sugarcane related.

In order to better control the cropland expansion associated to sugarcane expansion over 2000-2020, we adopted the representation of the AEZ in the Brazil-GLOBIOM version as described in (De Andrade Junior et al. 2019). It was implemented from 2010 onward as a spatially-explicit modulation of sugarcane production costs (proportionally to the AEZ suitability level), and restriction of new land conversions to sugarcane in the Amazon and the Pantanal biomes.

Improved biodiversity impact modeling

We also used in the improved model version for soy supply chains the methods developed in CLEVER D6.3 to connect Life Cycle Impact Assessment methods for biodiversity impacts to the land use, water use, GHG emissions and input use simulated by GLOBIOM, to provide novel biodiversity impact indicators. As summarized in Figure 2, these indicators provide estimates of time integrated future biodiversity impacts on freshwater and terrestrial ecosystems, resulting from multiple pressures estimated by GLOBIOM (land use occupation and transformation, water consumption for irrigation, as well as GHG emissions from agricultural activities and land use change, and phosphorus losses from cropland and pasture inputs).

Figure 2 - Overview of LC-Impact LCIA integration into GLOBIOM.

Derived from D6.2 Table 3. In the formulas EF: Environmental flow; CF: Characterization factors; LU: Land use type; LU_{from}: Land use type before transformation; LU_{to}: land use after transformation.

	ENVIRONMENTAL FLOW EF		CHARACTERISATION FACTORS CF				IMPACT		
	GLOBIOM Variable	Unit	Method	Damage on	Marginal/ avg	Impact considered	Unit	Formula	Unit
CLIMATE CHANGE	GHG emissions	CO2eq/year	LC-IMPACT	Freshwater and terrestrial	Average	All effects, 100y	PDF.y/kg	$EF \times CF$	PDF.y/year
LAND OCCUPATION	Land area per land use type	ha/year	LC-IMPACT D2.4	terrestrial	Average	na	PDF/(m ² .y)	$\sum_{LU} 1y * EF_{LU} * CF_{LU}$	PDF.y/year
LAND TRANSFORMATION	Land conversions between land use types	ha/year	LC-IMPACT D2.4	terrestrial	Average	100y	PDF.y/ha	$\sum_{LU_{from.to}} EF_{LU_{from.to}} * (CF_{LU_{to}} - CF_{LU_{from}})$	PDF.y/year
WATER CONSUMPTION	irrigation	km ³ /year	LC-IMPACT	Freshwater	Marginal	All effects	PDF.y/m ³	$EF \times CF$	PDF.y/year
FRESHWATER EUTROPHICATION	P inputs	tonnes P/year	LC-IMPACT	Freshwater	Average	Certain	PDF.y/kg	$EF \times CF$	PDF.y/year

Illustrative scenarios

To illustrate the model improvements, we generated projections with the improved model for soy supply chains from the initial year (2000) up to the year 2050 for three scenarios: the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) 1 (SSP1: Sustainability—taking the green road), 2 (SSP2: Middle of the Road) and 3 (SSP3: Regional rivalry—a rocky road). As further detailed in the CLEVER deliverable D6.3, the SSPs are a set of explorative scenarios designed to explore future challenges to climate change impacts and mitigation, have dedicated storylines for the main land-use sectors (Popp et al. 2017) – including contrasted trends for changes in demand, trade and technological progress – and have been widely used in global change analysis (O’Neill et al. 2020).

We consider SSP1-3 to illustrate how long-term trend could evolve by 2050, while the analysis in this deliverable will also focus on the historical period (2000-2020) and shorter term (e.g., 2030) with qualitative comparisons to authoritative short-term projections such as the OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2024-2033 (OECD and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2024).

Forest supply chains

GLOBIOM standard representation of forest sector

GLOBIOM includes forestry, forest industry and bioenergy modules as described in (Lauri et al. 2021) (Figure 3). The model is solved recursively for each 10-year period by maximizing the economic surplus (social welfare). In the forestry sector, the endogenous variables related to forest production activities and related land use and management, as well as biodiversity and carbon impacts are represented at subnational level: country boundaries intersected with spatial units of 5 arcmin to 2 arc-degree depending on the heterogeneity of altitude, soil and slope. The endogenous variables related to harvested wood products processing, trade and consumption are represented in the forest industry and bioenergy modules at the scale of 59 economic regions globally. Major countries, as well as all EU member States, are represented as individual model regions, while some regions are composed of multiple geographically proximate countries.

Figure 3 - Schematic representation of GLOBIOM forest sector representation.

Forest management

The standard version of the GLOBIOM model includes two forest land cover types: unmanaged (UnMngFor) and managed forests (MngFor). Unmanaged forests are forested land that has not been used historically for wood production. Managed forests are forested land that is currently used for production. The initial forest area in year 2000 is based on GLC2000 land-cover (Skalsky et al 2008), which is harmonized to match FAO's FRA (FAO, 2020) country-level data. The area evolution under the two forest types is based on the endogenous economic optimization of GLOBIOM according to wood demand levels, harvesting costs and land use change costs. Only agricultural land is assumed eligible for conversion to Energy crops woody plantations. In this version, there is no consideration of either industrial roundwood plantations, afforestation/deforestation or secondary forest management dynamics. The forest area is the sum of MngFor and UnMngFor.

Biomass Supply

Biomass supply is based on spatially explicit harvest potentials, spatially explicit harvest costs, spatially explicit transportation costs and forest/management type specific land-use change costs. Harvest potentials are based on increment data from the Global Forest Model (G4M) (G. E. Kindermann et al. 2006; G. Kindermann et al. 2008; Gusti and Kindermann 2011). G4M provides GLOBIOM estimates on initial biomass stock, growing stock and sustainable level of harvests as MAI (Mean Annual Increment) for each simulation unit.

The harvest costs are also based on G4M spatial explicit data. Transportation costs are based on Di Fulvio et al. (2016). Land-use change costs are linearly increasing as function of land demand, and are based on historical land-use change patterns. The purpose of land-use change costs is to control the transition between different forest and management types.

Forestry sector and wood industry

The forestry sector includes five harvested products (pulpwood, sawlogs, other industrial roundwood, fuelwood, logging residues). The forest industry sector includes the following products (Figure 4):

- four pulp grades: chemical pulp, mechanical pulp, recycled pulp, other fiber pulp
- three mechanical forest industry products: sawnwood, plywood, fiberboard
- four forest industry by-products: woodchips, sawdust, bark, black liquor
- recycled wood

Figure 4 - Schematic representation of global wood flows (Sankey diagram) in GLOBIOM for year 2010: from forest feedstocks to semi-finished wood products.

The bioenergy module includes two final products – traditional bioenergy (residential use fuelwood) and modern bioenergy (industrial use fuelwood) – and one intermediate product (wood pellets).

Forest industry and wood pellets production capacities are calibrated on FAOSTAT production data for 2000–2020. After 2020, production capacities evolve according to investment dynamics, where investment decisions are made by comparing the current period income and annualized investment costs. Forest industry and wood pellets production is modelled by using Leontief production technologies for converting primary forest products into secondary and by-products (eg. conversion of pulplogs into pulp and by-products), based on fixed input-output ratios. Leontief production technologies can be combined, which allows imperfect or perfect substitution between the inputs. The substitution between inputs can be further controlled by defining minimum/maximum shares for their use.

Wood demand

The demand for final products demand is based on constant elasticity demand functions, which are parametrized by reference volumes, reference prices and elasticity coefficients. Exceptions are modern bioenergy demand that are exogeneous and conventionally based on the SSP-RCP scenario data or specific exogenous demands aligned to SSP-RCPs from energy sector models (MESSAGE, PRIMES, POLES). Traditional bioenergy demand is assumed to stay constant over time. Price-elasticities lie between 0.1 and 1. Reference prices of the constant elasticity demand functions are based on the world export prices and transport costs, so that net exporters face world prices, and net importers face world prices plus transport costs (Buongiorno 2003). For simplicity, reference prices are assumed to stay constant over time. Reference volumes are based on FAOSTAT for 2000–2020. After 2020, the reference volumes are shifted over time based on GDP and population growth according to SSP-RCP scenario data, based on econometric estimates from (Buongiorno 2003; 2015; Morland et al. 2018). These estimates link per capita reference volume to per capita GDP through income-elasticities varying between 0 and 1, and differentiated for low, middle-and high-income regions. Newsprint and printing and writing papers are assumed to have 0 income elasticity for all regions.

Trade of forest products

Trade is modelled by using bilateral trade flows. Bilateral trade volumes are calibrated to BACI trade data for 2000–2020 (Gaulier and Zignago, 2010). After 2020, trade volumes evolve according to endogenous trade dynamics, which depend on constant elasticity trade-cost functions that are parametrized by historical trade volumes and transport costs. Transport costs are estimated from the difference between world import and export values similar to Buongiorno et al. (2003).

Improvements to forest cover and management dynamics

As summarized in Table 4 and further detailed in the following subsections, we improved the dynamics of forest cover and management change by introducing afforestation as well as forest plantations dedicated to roundwood production. Afforestation is assumed to be natural forests without harvest, and its area developments are based on historical data and scenario-specific external projections from the G4M model. Forest plantations dedicated to roundwood production are distinct from the energy wood plantations, and further split in two classes depending on the type of land cover replaced (forest, or non-forest land). We also have revised the classification of managed and unmanaged forests: we now distinguish different classes of natural forest (only partially protected and including one class of low intensity harvest) –, and seminatural forests (managed with medium to high harvest intensity). We also introduced a differentiation between coniferous and non-coniferous species for seminatural and plantation forests, and exogenous deforestation trends (based on historical trends and the G4M model).

Forest cover change

In the new model formulation, during 2000-2020, the forest area is calibrated to follow the dynamics and changes observed in country level afforestation and deforestation data from FAO's FRA (FAO, 2020). After 2020, forest area changes can be forced to G4M afforestation/deforestation data, and additional forest cover changes can be simulated endogenously in the model based on different deforestation/afforestation/plantation drivers. In particular, after year 2000, agricultural land expansion can lead to additional deforestation, and demand for wood as well as incentives for restoration or carbon sequestration can lead to additional forest expansion. Except for strictly protected natural forests and protected managed forests, all primary and secondary unmanaged forest as well as managed forests can be deforested.

Forest management

Table 5 provides an overview of the forest management classes in the new model formulation and the data sources used for the parameterization. Unmanaged forests are considered natural forests without harvest operations, and are divided between newly afforested areas after the year 2000 (AfrLnd), and "primary" (UnMngFor / PriFor) or "secondary" forests (UnMngFor / Cur0, UnMngFor / CurS) forest pre-existing in the year 2000. Secondary forests represent forests being under management in the past and not anymore managed, and are further separated depending on whether it is protected (CurS, based on WDPA classes I-III) or secondary forest not protected (Cur0).

Managed forests are split in different management intensity classes, that differ by the proportion of increment (G4M MAI=Mean Annual Increment) that can be harvested (up to a maximum threshold defined according to the specific management class). In high intensity management (CurC), the whole forest increment can be harvested while in medium (CurM) and low intensity (CurL) management, only part of the increment can be harvested (up to a maximum threshold defined according to each specific class). Consequently, harvest volumes can be increased by increasing the managed forest area or by intensifying forest management within the managed forest area, which translates into changing the management class or the share of MAI harvested within the same management class. The "low intensity" management

class is calibrated according to WDPA IUCN category I,II,III country areas. The “medium intensity” and “high intensity” are assumed together to match “production” forests inFAO’s FRA (FAO, 2020), and the model allocates endogenously the respective shares of each of these two classes based on economic criteria.

Table 4 - Summary of land management classification in GLOBIOM after the CLEVER 6.2 developments compared to the status quo model version.

Land management intensity	Management class GLOBIOM CLEVER	Management class GLOBIOM status quo
Natural forests	Afforestation, not harvested	NA
	Primary unmanaged forests in year 2000, not harvested	Unmanaged forests (UnMngFor)
	Secondary unmanaged forests in year 2000, not harvested	
	Strictly protected unmanaged forests, not harvested, cannot be deforested	
	Protected natural managed forests, low intensity harvest (close-to-nature forestry either non-coniferous or coniferous species), cannot be deforested	Managed forests (MngFor)
Seminatural forests	Managed forests, medium intensity harvest (Multifunctional forestry, either non-coniferous or coniferous species)	
	Managed forests, high intensity harvest (Long-rotation production forestry, either non-coniferous or coniferous species)	
Plantation forests (roundwood)	Forest plantation on old forest land (Short-rotation production forestry, either non-coniferous or coniferous species)	NA
Plantation forests (roundwood)	Forest plantation on new forest land (Short-rotation production forestry) , either non-coniferous or coniferous species	NA
Energy plantations (energywood)	Energy plantations, outside forest area	Energy plantations, outside forest area

Plantation forests (PltFor) expansion for roundwood production is driven by roundwood demand and they can be established inside or outside existing forest area. In the former case, they decrease managed forests (MngFor), but do not affect total forest area. In the latter case,

they increase total forest area similarly to afforestation effects by occupation of agricultural land.

The management areas assigned to the classes is based on a downscaling to grid cells based to Lesiv et al. (2022) global forest management map, which is harmonized to FAO's FRA (FAO, 2020) country level data to be consistent with FAO forest area definitions. Additionally, Initial protected areas are based on World Database of Protected Areas (WCMC 2020).

For natural forests, the spatially explicit biomass stocks and increments are based on G4M and harmonized to FRA (FAO, 2020) country level data. Spatially explicit harvest and transport costs are based on G4M and additional data from Di Fulvio et al. (2016) also in the new model version. For plantations, biomass stocks and increments are based on i3PGmix modelling.

We have introduced also a separation of plantation and managed forest area and wood supply according to Conifer (C) and Non-Conifer (NC) based on the FRA (FAO, 2020) country level growing stock data. For the EU, we use a separate spatially-explicit tree species dataset (Brus et al. 2012) for allocating the species to forest land. Tree species distribution is assumed to stay fixed over time, with C trees dominant in the boreal zone and NC trees in the tropical zone. In the temperate zone, C trees are dominant in some regions, and NC trees in other regions.

Table 5 - Forest management systems in GLOBIOM-CLEVER, and related data sources

Management system (GLOBIOM)	Description	Species group	Area calibration	Biomass / increment	Maximum share of increment harvestable (%)	Harvest/ transport costs
AfrLnd (Afforestation)	Unmanaged Natural forest , Afforestation	NA	FRA2020/G4M	G4M	0	NA
UnMngFor / PriFor (Primary forest)	Unmanaged Natural forest, Primary	NA	FRA2020/Lesiv2022	G4M	0	NA
UnMngFor / CurS (Secondary)	Unmanaged Natural forest, Strictly protected secondary	NA	WDPA categories I-III	G4M	0	NA
UnMngFor / Cur0 (Secondary)	Unmanaged Natural forest, other secondary	NA	Residual forest area	G4M	0	NA
MngFor / CurC_L (Low intensity)	Managed forest, close-to-nature and protected forest (protected)	Conifer	WDPA categories IV-VI	G4M	25 (EU)-50 (RoW)	G4M/ Di Fulvio et al. 2016
MngFor / CurNC_L (Low intensity)		Non-Conifer	WDPA categories IV-VI	G4M	25 (EU) -50(RoW)	G4M/ Di Fulvio et al. 2016
MngFor / CurC_M (Medium intensity)	Managed semi-natural forest, multifunctional forest	Conifer	FRA2020 /Lesiv2022	G4M	50 (EU)-75(RoW)	G4M/ Di Fulvio et al. 2016
MngFor / CurNC_M (Medium intensity)		Non-Conifer	FRA2020 /Lesiv2022	G4M	50 (EU) -75(RoW)	G4M/ Di Fulvio et al. 2016
MngFor / CurC (High intensity)	Managed semi-natural forest, Long rotation production forest	Conifer	FRA2020 /Lesiv2022	G4M	100	G4M/ Di Fulvio et al. 2016
MngFor / CurNC (High intensity)		Non-Conifer	FRA2020 /Lesiv2022	G4M	100	G4M/ Di Fulvio et al. 2016
PltFor (Roundwood plantations)	Short rotation production	Conifer & Non-Conifer	FRA2020/ Lesiv2022	3PGmix	100	Di Fulvio et al. 2016

Forest plantations

For forests classified as plantations within the forest area (FRA2020), we have created a subclass within the “high intensity” management and assumed that 100% of the increment is harvested and named them “roundwood plantations on old forest land”. This allows to segregate semi-natural forest areas where the intensity is relatively high (harvest range 50-100 MAI) and plantations areas where the management is very high (harvest forced to 100% MAI). At the same time, we have created a class of “forest plantations for roundwood in new forest areas” with the same increment as the ones modelled on forest land but expanding on agricultural land, where we forced also to harvest 100% of MAI. Specifically, we assumed that cropland and grassland land use categories can be converted to forest plantations established outside forest land. Finally, we have kept separate classification for “energy wood plantations” expanding outside forest land (in agricultural land), not considered as “forest land” and assumed to be eligible for conversion to agricultural land (Table 6).

We have retrieved the “forest plantation” area (within forest area, and named “FORPLANT”) at the country level for the historical period (year 2000, 2010, 2020) from FRA (FAO, 2020). For each of the years in the time series, the area at the national level were retrieved and assigned to each country within the total forest area. A downscaling from the national level to the GLOBIOM 2 arcdegree grid cells (ca. 200x200) km was obtained by using Lesiv et al. (2022) management map, by considering the class of “plantations” for distributing the national aggregate from FRA to each simulation grid cell.

Table 6 - Summary of the main advancements in forest plantation representation in CLEVER D6.2.

	Primary product	Land class suitable for expansion	Land use classification after plantation expansion	Increment Source
Roundwood Plantation on old* forest land (FORPLANT)	Sawlogs & Pulpwood & Fuelwood	Forest Land	Forest land	i3PGMIX short rotation
Roundwood Plantation on new** forest land (AGPLANT)	Sawlogs & Pulpwood & Fuelwood	Cropland & Grassland	Forest land	i3PGMIX short rotation
Energy Plantation (SRP)	Energywood	Cropland & Grassland	Cropland & Grassland	i3PGMIX short rotation

*Existing forest land in year 2020 **Area not included in forest land in year 2020

The past approach in GLOBIOM for explicitly representing wood yields for plantations was focused only on “short rotation energy plantations” (SRP) according to Aoki et al (2011). In this data source, yields for short-rotation tree plantations were collected from the most representative species (i.e., Eucalyptus, Acacia, Gmelina, Betula, Populus, Salix) and thus only

woody bioenergy crops. The yields were based on field-measured yields (i.e., as mean annual increments of stem wood) for different short-rotation tree species with proper management practices were first collected from various databases (dated between 1984 and 2006 and sourced from different global regions) and then upscaled to a global yield map based on the spatial patterns of potential net primary productivity (NPP) from (Cramer et al. 1999). The estimation of area potentials for tree plantations in the GLOBIOM maps followed an approach similar to the one proposed by (Zomer et al. 2008), including thresholds of tree growth based on aridity, temperature, elevation, population density and existing land cover (Havlík et al., 2011).

As a model advancement, we have used the spatial explicit wood increments derived from the i3PGMIX model, as described in CLEVER D6.1. These are included at the level of simulation units in GLOBIOM (2 arc degree). For roundwood plantations (FORPLANT, AGPLANT) we assume increments from i3PGMIX for short rotation cycles. The i3PGMIX yields for short rotation cycles were also applied to the “energy plantations” (SRP) and have replaced the increments derived previously from Aoki et al. (2011). For roundwood plantations, yields were calculated by applying deflators to i3PGMIX increments of 0.25 (pulpwood) to 0.5 (sawlogs), as a preliminary approach for addressing the yield obtainable when considering industrial roundwood assortments. For energy wood plantation the whole increment (whole tree biomass) from 3PGMIX MAI was assumed to be harvested.

When considering expansion of plantations in agricultural land according to their suitability areas and increments, we can observe that grid cells with harvest potentials exceeding 100,000 $\text{m}^3\text{year}^{-1}$ in both datasets are mostly in the South of Brazil. However, in the case of Aoki, some of the areas with high harvest potential extended also towards the Central and Northern region of Brazil. Overall, harvest potential for the whole country reaches a total of 6.7 Mm^3/year in i3PGMIX, that is almost half of the potential from Aoki et al. (12.0 Mm^3/year).

Figure 5 - Comparison of harvest potential (POT, thousand m^3/year) at the level of simulation grid cell (2 arc degree, $\approx 200 \times 200$ km) on suitable agricultural land according to Aoki (left) and i3PGMIX (right).

Biodiversity impacts

To account for the implications of forest management decisions on biodiversity, we have employed the well-established countryside Species Area Relationship (cSAR) model for a quantification of potentially disappeared fractions of global species (PDF) as a measure of the relative loss in species richness.

The cSAR model (Pereira, Ziv, and Miranda 2014) belongs to the family of SAR models, which measure the species richness with respect to habitat availability and is widely used in Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) to evaluate the impacts of products and services on biodiversity due to land use change. In the family of SAR models, the cSAR model distinguishes because it assumes that when transforming natural habitat, some species may adapt to human-modified habitat and therefore not all species will be lost, hence accounting for the use of both habitat categories by different functional species groups. Specifically, the indicator estimates the potential regional and global species loss (endemic). This can be interpreted as the number of species committed to extinction due to habitat loss, in comparison to an original scenario, on each ecoregion.

This biodiversity indicator is implemented using the land cover and land use information from GLOBIOM, and follows the methodology detailed in CLEVER D6.3 deliverable, with some adjustments. Initially, GLOBIOM grid cells are mapped to the relevant regions for the biodiversity indicator. In the cSAR model, species loss is specific for each WWF ecoregion. Subsequently, each land cover class and land use intensity class is mapped to the cSAR models land cover categories, in which characterization factors (CFs) are defined. Specifically, we have used CFs for land occupation from (Scherer et al. 2023) for a quantification of global species loss from land use. With the total areas differentiated by land cover and the respective biodiversity coefficients, the total biodiversity score for the biodiversity indicator is calculated at the grid, regional and global scales.

The CFs for plantations reported in Scherer et al. (2023) have generally impacts significantly higher than any other land use occupation class (also of cropland intense and comparable to urban land), due to the inclusion in the same category of a very large sets of fruits, oils and wood plantations (e.g., including palm oil and coffee). For a better differentiation of forest and energy plantations with other land use categories, we have assumed that plantations have the same CFs as the “cropland minimal” from Scherer et al. 2023, given the closeness of plantations to perennial agricultural crops included in this class.

Table 7 - Mapping between GLOBIOM management classes and the biodiversity models' coefficient.

GLOBIOM land management intensity	cSAR land use intensity CFs
Cropland High input	Cropland intense
Cropland Low input	Cropland light
Cropland Subsistence farming	Cropland minimal
Grassland	Pasture light
Natural vegetation land	Natural habitat (no impact)
Primary forests (PriFor)	Natural habitat (no impact)
Secondary non harvested forests (Cur0)	Secondary vegetation (no impact)
Strictly protected forests (CurS)	Natural habitat, Secondary vegetation (no impact)
Low intensity management forests (CurL)	Managed forest minimal
Medium intensity management forests (CurM)	Managed forest light
High intensity (CurC)	Managed forest intense
Plantation on old forest land (CurH) (FORPLANT)	Cropland minimal
Plantation on new forest land (AGPLANT)	Cropland minimal
Energy plantations (SRP)	Cropland minimal

Improvements to forestry supply chain modelling

New final products/sectors

The forest sector has about 50 different product categories, which can be divided to primary products, by-products, semifinished products, final (aggregated) products sectors, recycled products and aggregated final products. The model operates in disaggregated product level, but product aggregates (i.e., sectors) are used for calibration when disaggregate data are not available, and we include the following new final products/product aggregates: construction, furniture, wood-packaging, paper and paperboards, wood-based textiles and bio-plastic. The demand functions for semi-finished products (chemical pulp, mechanical pulp, dissolving pulp, sawnwood, plywood, fiberboard) were replaced by demand functions for these sectorial final product aggregates.

Data for paper and paperboards (production, consumption, trade) in 2000-2020 is based on FAOSTAT. After 2020 production and trade are endogenous while consumption is based on demand functions, which are shifted by GDP and Population growth. The remaining new sectors are not included in FAOSTAT and comparable data is not generally available from other sources. For this reason, we apply a simplified approach for them, where data in 2000-2020 is generated from FAOSTAT semifinished products data and aggregated to the final products by using country level shares for each sector from (Mantau et al. 2010). After 2020, the remaining final products demand is based on semi-finished product demand or some additional data on final products future demand taken from other models/studies (e.g. Mishra et al. 2022).

For pulpwood originating in GLOBIOM from “tropical” regions, we assumed the exclusive sourcing from plantations, while pulpwood sourcing from natural forests can be occur in boreal and temperate regions.

Figure 6 - Sankey diagram with a demonstrative example of the main forest product categories included including the final products aggregates (values are only exemplificative).

C/NC products

In the improved version for this deliverable, forest sector products and processing activities are further separated according to two tree species groups (C=coniferous, NC=non-coniferous). The separation is applied for all products except: fiberboard, paper and paperboard and bioenergy products. The separation is not applied for these products, because they are often produced from a mixture of C and NC biomass. The separation is based on FAOSTAT production and trade data where available, or when FAOSTAT data is not available, the separation is approximated by using regional C and NC biomass resource balances. For fiberboard, newsprint, printing and writing papers and bioenergy production C and NC biomass are assumed to be perfect substitutes, which implies that the share of C and NC biomass can vary between 0 and 100%. For packaging materials and other papers production the minimum share of C biomass is assumed to be 75%. C/NC separation improves competitiveness of boreal and temperate zones relative to tropical zone, because these regions have higher C-biomass harvest potential and C-biomass is preferred raw material for forest industry process and final consumption.

Recycling

The model has been extended to include paper and paperboard recycling, based on the forest-only version of the model (see Lauri et al., 2021). Moreover, we now separate sawnwood recycling and reuse as different processes. Sawnwood recycling means that sawnwood can be reused after its lifetime for lower quality products (fiberboard, energy wood). Sawnwood reuse means sawnwood can be reused after its lifetime again for sawnwood. An Important difference is that sawnwood reuse decreases the need for new sawlogs and roundwood harvests while sawnwood recycling does not affect so much on harvests. The reason is that fiberboard raw materials and energy wood are usually not harvested roundwood, but by-products and logging residues.

Recycled (R) biomass can be used to substitute virgin fibers in wood-based products production. Due to material losses and the ageing of recycled biomass it is not possible to substitute all virgin fibers with R biomass, but there are maximum technical shares for R biomass use. The model includes three R products: R wood, R paper and R pulp. R wood is recovered from mechanical forest industry products, which are re-used as a raw material in fiberboard production or burned for energy. R paper is recovered paper and paperboard, which is re-used for R pulp production. R pulp is used as a raw material in paper and paperboard production. The supply of R wood is based on the final consumption of mechanical forest industry products and on R wood collection rates. The maximum R wood collection rate is assumed to be 50% based on Mantau et al (2010). The supply of R paper is based on FAOSTAT statistics for 2000–2020. After 2020, R paper supply is endogenous and is determined by paper and paperboard consumption and R paper collection rates. The maximum R paper collection rate is assumed to be 80% based on observed maximum national collection rates (European Paper Recycling Council 2019). The supply of R pulp depends on the supply of R paper and R pulp yield from R paper. R pulp yield from R paper depends on the filler content of R paper, and the ageing effect of R biomass. The average R pulp yield with the ageing effect is about 90%. Connecting this to the filler content of different paper grades (packaging materials 0%, newsprint 10% and printing and writing papers 20%) gives recycled pulp yield of 70–90% depending on the paper grade. Other papers are assumed to have zero yields, since they mainly include sanitary papers, which are usually not recycled. Connecting the R pulp yields to maximum collection rates and the consumption shares of different paper grades implies that the maximum technical share of R pulp varies from 60% to 65% at the global level.

Illustrative scenarios

To illustrate the model improvements described above on forest management areas, wood harvest volumes, carbon stocks and wood trade, we have designed preliminary test scenarios with the parameterization of the supply chain.

All scenarios are based on the same socioeconomic developments in terms of GDP and Population, where future global growth is considered under SSP2 (Business As Usual socioeconomic growth, see also CLEVER deliverable D6.3). Mitigation ambitions through biomass use were considered by means of RCP scenarios. In particular, we have considered the RCP1.9 from the MESSAGE model. Default bioenergy demands was changed in the RCP1p9 from “old” overshooting scenarios to “no-overshoot” net zero scenarios. The Net Zero scenario generated from the old overshooting scenario by decreasing bioenergy demand -50%, which is close to ENGAGE database net zero bioenergy demand scenario. This is also more consistent with new i3PGmix plantation forest data where increments are much lower than before. We have considered this combination of socioeconomic and mitigation scenario (SSP2-RCP1p9) to showcase impacts on forest land in scenarios where there is a relatively high demand on biomass from forests, given the summing up of increasing demands driven by population growth together with a global mitigation high ambition. In this scenario, global roundwood demand increases 19% by 2050 and 36% by 2100 compared to 2020 levels.

On top of these trends, we differentiate alternative developments of forest area use across three scenarios:

BASE: business as usual scenario, where the management intensity and forest industry resource efficiency mimic the behavior of the model before CLEVER improvements in that the potential for additional biomass supply from roundwood forest plantations is ignored. This scenario excludes the expansion of forest plantations for roundwood (either within forest area or on agricultural land) after 2020.

FORPLANT: Forest management intensifies by allowing plantations for roundwood production to expand in already existing natural/seminatural forest land (Management adjustment on the intensive margin).

AGPLANT: Plantations are for production of roundwood allowed to expand only in agricultural land outside the forest land (Management adjustment on the extensive margin).

These three different scenarios represent different supply strategies able to satisfy future demands for forest biomass. The BASE scenario represents a scenario where future demands are satisfied only by existing forest resources, without the option to rely on the most intensive form of forest management (roundwood forest plantations). FORPLANT represents a scenario continuing the historical expansion of plantations within forest land and continuing an historical trend of decreasing natural forest resources. At the other extreme we find the AGPLANT scenario, where expansion of plantation is entirely sourced from non-forest land, thereby releasing the pressure from natural forests. The comparison of AGPLANT, FORPLANT and BASE is useful for understanding future impacts of alternative land use policies on forest resources

and implication in terms of harvest volumes, trade and biodiversity. All scenarios are simulated recursively in the GLOBIOM model and results reported for the period 2000-2100 with time steps of 10 years (see “Results & Discussion” session).

Table 8 - Illustrative scenarios considered in this report for forest supply chains.

BASE	SSP2_RCP1p9_BASE BAU socioeconomic development High mitigation demand Baseline forest area development (plantations stable at 2020 level)
FORPLANT	SSP2_RCP1p9_FORPLANT BAU socioeconomic development High mitigation demand Expansion of plantations within existing forest area (2020)
AGPLANT	SSP2_RCP1p9_AGPLANT BAU socioeconomic development High mitigation demand Expansion of plantations in areas outside existing forest area (2020)

Aquaculture and aquafeed supply chains

The GLOBIOM fish module and business-as-usual scenario parameterization

Module overview

The GLOBIOM Fish module covers key blue food supply chains, with an endogenous representation of demand, trade, processing and production for fish products, and connections to the agricultural supply chains in other parts of GLOBIOM (Spillias et al., 2025). As summarized in Figure 7, the fish production covers both the catch from marine fisheries and the supply from aquaculture production systems, including fed and non-fed production systems. The processing and reduction sectors transform production into final products, waste and fish meal and fish oil (FMFO) products, with FMFO also being used as aquafeed to aquaculture, together with crop-based aquafeed. The Fish module is connected to the GLOBIOM agricultural sector through the demand in crop products for aquafeed, and the assumptions about possible substitution between blue foods and other food products.

Figure 7 - Schematic overview of the GLOBIOM Fish module

As detailed in Table 9, the module covers ten major aggregated groups of fish products, including include all major types of finfish, bivalves, and cephalopods, whilst excluding marine mammals, seaweeds, and other marine products such as sponges and echinoderms. In addition to these final products, the model considers 10 primary fish products (matching the 10 aggregated final products) as well as additional 12 intermediate products related to waste (10 products matching each primary products), fish meal and fish oil.

Table 9 - List of final aggregated products in the GLOBIOM Fish module, and correspondence to FAOSTAT product categories

FAOSTAT Products	GLOBIOM Aggregated final fish products	
CRABS, SEA-SPIDERS	Crustaceans (CRST)	
KINGCRABS, SCALLOPS, CRAB LOBSTERS		
KRILL, PLANKTONIC CRUSTACEANS		
LOBSTERS, SPINY-ROCK LOBSTERS		
MISCELLANEOUS MARINE CRUSTACEANS		
FRESHWATER CRUSTACEANS		
SHRIMPS, PRAWNS	Shrimps and Prawns (SHRI)	
CARPS, BARBELS AND OTHER CYPRINIDS	Freshwater Fishes (FRSH)	
TILAPIAS AND OTHER CICHLIDS		
MISCELLANEOUS FRESHWATER FISHES		
MISCELLANEOUS DIADROMOUS FISHES		
RIVEREELS		
SHADS		
STURGEONS, PADDLEFISHES		
SALMONS, TROUTS, SMELTS		Salmons and Trouts (SALM)
FLOUNDERS, HALIBUTS, SOLES		Demersal Fishes (DRMS)
MISCELLANEOUS DEMERSAL FISHES		
CODS, HAKES, HADDOCKS		
MARINE FISHES NOT IDENTIFIED	Marine Fishes (MARN)	
SHARKS, RAYS, CHIMAERAS		
MISCELLANEOUS COASTAL FISHES		
MISCELLANEOUS PELAGIC FISHES	Pelagic Fishes (PELG)	
HERRINGS, SARDINES, ANCHOVIES	Tunas (TUNA)	
TUNAS, BONITOS, BILLFISHES		
SQUIDS, CUTTLEFISHES, OCTOPUSES	Cephalopods (CEPH)	
ABALONES, WINKLES, CONCHS	Molluscs (MLSC)	
CLAMS, COCKLES, ARK SHELLS		
FRESHWATER MOLLUSCS		
MISCELLANEOUS MARINE MOLLUSCS		
MUSSELS		
OYSTERS		
SCALLOPS, PECTENS		

Following the supply categories from FAOSTAT, the demand for primary products can be supplied at country level by different production systems: wild capture or aquaculture, the later being further differentiated in two dimensions (fed or non-fed, and freshwater, brackish or marine environments). Table 10 provides a mapping of the primary products by each production systems.

Table 10 - Mapping of primary products and production systems in the GLOBIOM Fish module. An x indicates that the combination of primary product and production system is considered in the model. Combinations with an x are only present in countries were FAOSTAT reports so.

	CRST	SHRI	FRSH		SALM	DMRS	MARN	PELG	TUNA	CEPH	MLSC
Catch	x	x	x		X	x	x	x	x	x	x
Fed / Freshwater	x	x	x		X	x	x				
Fed / Brackish		x	x			x		x			
Fed / Marine									x		
Non-Fed / Freshwater	x	x	x			x	x	x		x	x
Non-Fed / Brackish		x	x				x	x			x
Non-Fed / Marine		x							x		x

Key principles, data sources and equations for a business-as-usual projection

The module relies on a database of historical fish demand and supply over 2000-2019 consolidated from FAOSTAT data for the supply (production data at country level by type of fish, environment and FAO fishery region) and demand (food balance sheets disaggregated into food, feed, other uses and exports) of fish products. We also use additional data sources, including FAOSTAT data for trade and processing rates, and additional data sources for waste from processing (Koueta, Viala, and Le Bihan 2014; James et al. 2011), reduction ratios (Péron, François Mittaine, and Le Gallic 2010), feed requirements from FMFO and crops (Tacon and Metian 2008; 2015; Froehlich, Runge, et al. 2018).

Based on this data resource, we initialize the model for the year 2000, and generate parameters used for key equations in subsequent projections. In these projections:

- the assumed level of demand for each fish final product and region is based on observed levels of demand (up to 2020) and future trends (after 2020) in population and per capita consumption patterns and price elasticities. The demand for final and intermediate products (including aquafeed) is linked to processing (including reduction) of primary and intermediate products, supply of primary products and trade of final products (which has to balance out globally) via the market balance equation [1] in Table 11.
- the supply of primary products is controlled by assumptions capacity constraints based on observed levels (up tot 2020) and scenario-specific assumptions (after 2020). A baseline future scenario can be for example assume a stable or reducing capacity for catch and non-fed aquaculture, and no constraint on fed aquaculture. The supply of primary products of various sources at regional scale is linked to assumed capacity constraints via the supply constraint equation [2] in Table 11, and additional minimum and maximum bounds that can be scenario specific (equations [5] and [6] in Table 11).

For a business-as-usual scenario, we seek to preserve observed regional market shares until 2020 (i.e., minimum and maximum bounds follow historical observations over 2000-2020 with a 20% margin) for all supply sources, and 2020 regional market shares after 2020 for aquaculture sources (i.e., minimum and maximum bounds follow 2020 regional supply multiplied by globally aggregated demand shifter with a 20% margin).

- the processing and reduction sectors dynamics are linked to primary product supply and final product demand dynamics via assumptions about input - output coefficients as well as assumptions about bounds for the share of specific primary and waste products in reduction sector input (see equation [3] in Table 11), and possible reduction activities in each region. Input-output coefficients include waste ratios (i.e., amount of output waste and final product per unit of input primary product in processing sector) and reduction ratios (i.e., amount of output fish meal and fish oil produced per unit of input waste and primary product in the reduction sector). Reduction ratios are considered constant over time, the shares of pelagic fish (respectively, waste) in reduction sector input is assumed to decrease (respectively increase) over 2000-2050, while reduction activities are limited to where observed regions over 2000-2020.
- the feed requirements for fed aquaculture (including both fish meal and fish oil and crop aquafeeds) is linked to the dynamics of fed aquaculture production via assumptions about primary product- and production system-specific input-output coefficients (see Feed balance equation [4] in Table 11). These input-output coefficients encompass information on feed conversion ratios and the share of different aquafeeds (FMFO and crops). These coefficients are first estimated for the historical period from various sources (Tacon & Metian 2008, Tacon & Metian 2015, Froehlich et al 2018b), and then extrapolated to 2050 based on general-additive models for each species group (see also scenario description section). It should be noted that the share of fish meal & fish oil in total aquafeed input is directly estimated from Tacon & Metian 2015, while we make the additional assumption that the remainder of fish requirements is derived from crop-based aquafeeds.
- Final products can be traded across regions. Due to the lack of reliable data on the trade of fish products, only total exports and imports between each region and the rest of the world are modelled. This contrasts with agricultural commodities, for which bilateral trade between each region pairs is modelled.

The key equations detailed in Table 11 rely on the following notations:

Model sets

R GLOBIOM regions (37 in this model version)

C GLOBIOM countries

p GLOBIOM products (10 primary products, 12 intermediate products, 10 final products)

G groups of GLOBIOM products (pelagic fish, waste)

s GLOBIOM production source (catch, fed aquaculture, non-fed aquaculture, distinguished by primary product)

Model variables

$S(C,p,s)$ supply from region R and production source s of product p (primary product only) [ton product]

$I(R,p)$ and $E(R,p)$ respectively total imports and total exports of product p in region R [ton product]

$P(R,p,p')$ processing in region R of product p (either primary or intermediate) into product p' (either intermediate or final) [ton product]

$F(R,p)$ demand for product p (intermediate product) as aquafeed [ton product]

$D(R,p)$ final demand for food and other uses of product p (final product) in region R [ton product]

Model parameters

$P_SC(C,p,s)$ capacity constraint in Country C for production source s and primary product p

$P_RB(G)$ global bounds for share of aggregated product groups G in total inputs to reduction sector

$P_FR(R,s,p,p')$ aquafeed requirement in Region R and production source s (fed aquaculture) for input product p' per unit output product p {t input per t output}

$P_ABMI(R,p,s)$ minimum supply volume for Region R, product p and source s

$P_ABMA(R,p,s)$ maximum supply volume for Region R, product p and source s

Table 11 - Overview of main equations in the improved GLOBIOM Fish module

[1]	Market balance	For each R and p, $SUM(s \text{ and } C \text{ in } R, S(C,p,s)) + I(R,p) + SUM(p', P(R,p',p)) = E(R,p) + Sum(p', P(R,p,p')) + F(R,p) + D(R,p)$
[2]	Supply capacity	For each C, s and p, $S(C,p,s) < P_SC(C,p,s)$
[3]	Global reduction input bounds	For each aggregated of G groups of reduction input products, $SUM(R, p', p \text{ in } G, P(R,p,p')) / SUM(R, p', \text{all } p, P(R,p,p')) > P_RB(G)$
[4]	Feed balance	For each R and aquafeed product p (including crops), $F(R,p) > SUM(p', SUM(s \text{ and } C \text{ in } R, S(C,p',s)) * P_FR(R,s,p,p'))$
[5]	Regional supply min. bound	For each R, s and fish product p, $SUM(C \text{ in } R, S(C,p,s)) > P_ABMI(R,p, S)$
[6]	Regional supply max. bound	For each R, s and fish product p, $SUM(C \text{ in } R, S(C,p,s)) < P_ABMA(R,p, S)$

Selected model improvements for aquaculture and aquafeed supply chains

Stabilizing regional patterns of supply after 2020

As detailed above, in the standard version of the GLOBIOM fish module, the regional patterns of supply for various sources (catch, fed and non-fed aquaculture) are constrained by historical data until 2020. After 2020, they follow scenario-specific assumptions: in our representation of a business-as-usual future, catch is not allowed to go beyond 2020 levels and aquaculture is expected to provide for the additional supply. While in the standard GLOBIOM fish module version the regional patterns of aquaculture supply are not constrained after 2020, we introduced species and aquaculture production system-level minimum and maximum bounds to limit possible deviations from the historical share of each region in the global output (equations [5] and [6] detailed in previous section).

Biodiversity impacts from crop aquafeeds

In order to better capture the biodiversity impacts associated with the crop aquafeeds, we added to the model version containing the GLOBIOM Fish module the biodiversity impact indicators derived by combining GLOBIOM and LC-IMPACT characterization factors, as developed in task 6.3 and presented in CLEVER D6.3. As summarized in Figure 8, these indicators provide estimates of time integrated future biodiversity impacts on freshwater and terrestrial ecosystems, resulting from multiple pressures estimated by GLOBIOM (land use occupation and transformation, water consumption for irrigation, as well as GHG emissions from agricultural activities and land use change, and phosphorus losses from cropland and pasture inputs).

Figure 8 - Overview of LC-Impact LCIA integration into GLOBIOM.

Derived from D6.2 Table 3. In the formulas EF: Environmental flow; CF: Characterization factors; LU: Land use type; LU_{from}: Land use type before transformation; LU_{to}: land use after transformation.

	ENVIRONMENTAL FLOW		CHARACTERISATION FACTORS CF				IMPACT		
	GLOBIOM Variable	Unit	Method	Damage on	Marginal/ avg	Impact considered	Unit	Formula	Unit
CLIMATE CHANGE	GHG emissions	CO2eq/year	LC-IMPACT	Freshwater and terrestrial	Average	All effects, 100y	PDF.y/kg	$EF \times CF$	PDF.y/year
LAND OCCUPATION	Land area per land use type	ha/year	LC-IMPACT D2.4	terrestrial	Average	na	PDF/(m ² .y)	$\sum_{LU} 1y * EF_{LU} * CF_{LU}$	PDF.y/year
LAND TRANSFORMATION	Land conversions between land use types	ha/year	LC-IMPACT D2.4	terrestrial	Average	100y	PDF.y/ha	$\sum_{LU_{from.to}} EF_{LU_{from.to}} * (CF_{LU_{to}} - CF_{LU_{from}})$	PDF.y/year
WATER CONSUMPTION	irrigation	km ³ /year	LC-IMPACT	Freshwater	Marginal	All effects	PDF.y/m ³	$EF \times CF$	PDF.y/year
FRESHWATER EUTROPHICATION	P inputs	tonnes P/year	LC-IMPACT	Freshwater	Average	Certain	PDF.y/kg	$EF \times CF$	PDF.y/year

Nitrogen losses from finfish aquaculture production

In order to provide additional indicators related to the environmental impacts from aquaculture, we estimated the amount of nitrogen waste associated with aquaculture. This impact is estimated as species- and aquaculture system-specific amount of waste per unit of output (ton Nitrogen per unit ton of output, estimated from literature), multiplied by the species- and aquaculture system-specific amount of aquaculture output (ton output).

The estimates of the amount of waste per unit of output are derived from mass balance equations drawn from a biophysical model for aquaculture systems (Baldan et al. 2018), and data on N content in feeds and N retention efficiencies from the INRAE-CIRAD-AFZ Feed Tables (Sauvant et al. 2004). The latter only covers salmonids: we estimated that the values could only be extrapolated to other finfish groups, while additional data acquisition is necessary to be able to cover molluscs (MLSC), cephalopods (CEPH), shrimps & prawns (SHRI) groups and other crustaceans (CRST).

Illustrative scenarios

To illustrate the potential impacts on terrestrial biodiversity of future developments in the demand of crop aquafeeds, we used the GLOBIOM fish module to generate projections of crop aquafeeds, their land use requirements and associated biodiversity impacts to 2050 for 2 scenarios.

Description of scenarios

The first scenario considered, denoted **BAU**, represents a business as usual projection, that is characterized over the 2000-2020 period by a reproduction of historical trends, and a prolongation of those from 2020 to 2050 based on the 'Middle of the Road' Shared Socioeconomic Pathway (SSP2) scenario and the following additional assumptions for the blue food sectors:

- The demand for blue food products follows SSP2 region-specific population projections, and product- and region-specific projections of per capita demand levels. Similarly to agricultural final products in the model, the per capita product demand levels are derived from GDP/cap projections and product- and region-specific relationships between GDP/cap and product demand estimated on historical data.
- The capacity of marine catch and non-fed aquaculture follow historical trends over 2000-2020, and are kept constant after 2020, reflecting a stagnation of these sources of blue food supply
- The minimum and maximum bounds for regional supply follow historical patterns for both catch and aquaculture until 2020 (with a 20% margin), and, for aquaculture only, 2020 regional market shares multiplied by globally aggregated demand shifters after 2020 (with a 20% margin).
- The bounds for the share of waste (resp. catch of forage fish) in fish meal and fish oil production are assumed to increase (resp. decrease) over 2000-2050, reflecting historical trends until 2020 and a prolongation of those after. The maximum share of waste increase from 0.1 in 2020 to 0.6 in 2050, and that of forage fish decreases from 0.6 in 2020 to 0.1 in 2050.
- The aquafeed requirements increase over 2000-2050 due to total production increase, despite decreases in feed requirements per unit of fed-aquaculture output over the same time period. Crop aquafeed products progressively replace fish meal and fish oil aquafeed. These are a result the following assumed trends:
 - The economic feed conversion ratio (EFCR, providing an estimate of how much input is required to produce one unit of output) decreases over 2000-2050, reflecting increased feed efficiency trends estimated from Tacon & Metian (2015) until 2020, and a prolongation of those over 2020-2050 (using generalized additive models). Depending on the product, EFCR values range between 1.3 and 2.4 in 2000, between 1.3 and 1.8 in 2020 and between 1.1 and 1.4 in 2050.

- The share of fishmeal and fish oil in total aquafeed input decrease over 2000-2050 and are replaced by crop aquafeeds, reflecting estimated trends from Tacon & Metian (2008) until 2020, and a prolongation of those over 2020-2050 (using generalized additive models). Depending on the product, the share of fish meal and fish oil in total aquafeed input ranges between 0.12 and 0.60 in 2000, between 0.02 and 0.14 in 2020 and between 0.00 and 0.01 in 2050.
- The share of various crops in total crop aquafeeds remains stable over 2000-2050, reflecting assumptions for 'current' and '2050 BAU' scenarios from (Froehlich, Runge, et al. 2018).

In addition to the baseline scenario, we consider one alternative scenario (**AF20**) varying assumptions on future trends in aquafeed composition. In this scenario, both the composition of various aquafeed products (fish meal, fish oil, individual crops) in total feed requirements, and the feed conversion efficiency are maintained to the same level as in 2020. It therefore differs from the BAU scenario, that assumes after 2020 an increasing share of crops in aquafeed, and an increasing feed conversion efficiency. This scenario allow testing an assumption with a lower (resp. higher) share of crops (resp. fish meal and fish oil) in aquafeeds, and lower fed aquaculture efficiency, everything else equal.

Projections of impacts

We use the updated version of the GLOBIOM including the GLOBIOM Fish module to project the above-mentioned scenario until 2050, and analyse results on total blue demand, aquaculture supply, the total aquafeed use and its composition between crop and fish meal & fish oil aquafeeds, and various sustainability aspects such as volume of forage fish processed by the reduction sector, land use change, and biodiversity impacts from land use and land use change.

We expect the analysis of the **BAU** scenario to be helpful to understand temporal developments of aquaculture, aquafeed and their sustainability impacts. However, some impacts of crop aquafeed use may occur in other regions that where consumed as aquafeed (e.g., deforestation associated with imported crop feed), and may be hard to uncover without a detailed tracing of commodity flows across regions and uses, which is not available in this model version. However, the comparison of **differences between the BAU scenario and the AF20 scenario** in both crop aquafeed use and impacts by 2050 is expected to shed more light as to the specific impact of varying share of crop products in total aquafeed.

ILLUSTRATIVE PROJECTIONS AND DISCUSSION

Soy supply chains

Results from illustrative projections

Demand for oilseed products

The globally aggregated projected demand for various end uses (Feed, Food, Biofuel, Other uses) of oilseed crop (Soya, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Oil palm) products for the illustrative scenarios with the improved version GLOBIOM are presented in Figure 9. It pictures an increase in global consumption over 2000-2020 (more than a doubling, from 255 million ton [Mt) to 546 Mt), and further increases from 2020 to 2050 for all three SSP scenarios (2050 levels range across SSPs of 705-874 Mt, i.e., a 2020-2050 increase of +29-60%). Both recent and future increases (as well as differences across SSPs) in demand are dominated by the demand for livestock feed, while demand for biofuel remains stable beyond 2020 (by assumption), and demand for food and other uses moderately increases.

Figure 9 - Projections of consumption levels for oilseed products from Oil palm, Rapeseed, Soya and Sunflower with the improved model version, from 2010 to 2050 for SSP2, and 2050 values for SSP1 and SSP3.

Although not fully comparable due to differences in product (e.g., groundnut and cotton are not included in GLOBIOM results presented here and copra is not included in GLOBIOM), end use (e.g., demand for aquafeed is not covered in this version of GLOBIOM) and supply chain flow (e.g., the recycling of vegetable oil waste from food use into biofuel use is not considered in

GLOBIOM) coverage, the GLOBIOM projections are well in line with that of the OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2024-2033 (OECD and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2024). The latter projects about 20% higher total consumption levels (in particular for feed and food use) over 2010-2020 (which are likely due to differences in crop and end use coverage, and possibly different assumptions about livestock feed rations from 2000 onwards) and a slight increase in projected biofuel consumption between 2020-2030 (resulting from differences in assumptions). Yet, it provides a qualitatively and quantitatively comparable picture of growing demand for oilseed products, with feed as the most important demand component, and feed and food as important contributors to future growth in demand after 2020.

The differences across SSP scenarios by 2050 reflect diverging assumptions about several factors, including population (highest in SSP3 with 9.8 billion people and lowest in SSP1 with 8.3 billion people), income (proxied through GDP per capita, highest in SSP1 and lowest in SSP3) and dietary preferences (with a shift away from animal products assumed for SSP1), leading to the lowest (resp. highest) increase in livestock and oilseed products for SSP1 (resp. SSP2). It should however be noted that in SSP1, although the demand for oilseed crops and cakes are lowest, the demand for vegetable oil is high, and higher than for other scenarios.

Producing and crushing of primary oilseed crops

As described in Figure 10, the global trends and regional patterns in the production and crushing of primary oilseed crops differ across crops. As compared to other oilseed crops, the production and crushing of soya shows a faster increase over 2020-2050 than other oilseed crops. Soya also shows more contrast across SSP scenarios than other oilseed crops in projected 2050 production and crushing levels: values are markedly lower for SSP1 for soya instead of slightly higher for other crops. This reflects the SSP1 assumptions about livestock product consumption and the relatively higher level of soya to feed use than other oilseed crops.

Figure 10 - Projections of global primary oilseed crop production (left panels) and crushing (right panels), split by region for Soya (upper panels) and other oilseed crops (oil palm, rapeseed and sunflower) with the improved model version, from 2010 to 2050 for SSP2, and 2050 values for SSP1 and SSP3.

Figure 10 also illustrates that crushing regional patterns can differ from that of primary crop production, in particular for soya. While Brazil and USA remain the largest producers, China and the rest of the world started to become significant regions for soybean crushing, and India could become an important crushing region after 2020.

The patterns from in Figure 10 over 2010-2030 are broadly consistent with the historical trends and projections to 2030 from OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2024-2033 (OECD and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2024), with for example a good agreement in the amount and regional patterns of crushing. Some fine-tuning might still be needed to match more closely the historical trends, in particular for largest countries in terms of production of crushing, such as India for rapeseed (overestimated by GLOBIOM in illustrative projections), and for soy supply chains (e.g., Brazil production is slightly underestimated by GLOBIOM in illustrative projections).

Net trade in soya and other oilseed crop products

As illustrated in Figure 11, for both 2020 net export volumes and 2020-2050 increase in net exports, soya bean (resp. soya protein cake) dominates the trade of oilseed primary crops (resp. protein cakes). Oil palm dominates the current trade in vegetable oils, with stable levels over the 2020-2050 period. Brazil, USA and Argentina are the largest exporters of soya-based products in 2020, while China and to a lower extent EU are major importers of both soya bean and protein meals. These trade patterns are expected to amplify over 2020-2050 in SSP2, with India appearing as a new hub for soya crushing (with increasing soya imports and soya protein meal export), favoured by the increasing demand for vegetable oil in India (more than a doubling over 2020-2050) outpacing that of livestock products (close to a doubling over 2020-2050). SSP1 departs from other SSPs by 2050, with lower exports of soya bean and soya protein cake, and an increase level of trade in other primary oilseed crops and protein meals, and soy oil. This relates to the assumed shift in dietary preferences in SSP1, leading to a lower consumption of animal products than in other SSPs, with impacts varying across regions depending on the extent to which the production and crushing of primary oilseed products connects to domestic oil and protein meals.

Figure 11 - Projections of net trade in oilseed products (primary crops, protein meals and vegetable oils, each split between soya and other oilseed crops) across selected GLOBIOM regions and the rest of the world (ROW), with the improved model version, from 2010 to 2050 for SSP2, and 2050 values for SSP1 and SSP3.

Similarly to other components of the market balance, there is a relatively good agreement with the OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2024-2023 for 2010-2030 levels of trade in various oilseed

products, but some fine-tuning might be needed to more closely match historical trends and projections to 2030 for various oilseed products. For example, GLOBIOM projections for the illustrative scenarios might underestimate the exports of protein meals (including Argentina exports).

Soy production systems in Brazil

As illustrated in Figure 12, the projections for the illustrative scenarios with the improved model broadly reproduce the 2000-2020 increase in soy harvested areas and the emergence of soy-corn double cropping at national scale. According to IBGE PAM statistics, total harvested area increased from 14.1 million hectares in 2000 to 23.1 million hectares in 2010 (22.9 in GLOBIOM projections) and 37.6 million hectares in 2020 (40.1 in GLOBIOM projections), and soya-corn double cropping (interpreted as the second harvest corn in IBGE PAM statistics) represented 0% of total soy harvested areas in 2000, 24% in 2010 (28% in GLOBIOM projections) and 35% in 2020 (36% in GLOBIOM projections).

Figure 12 - Historical values (from IBGE PAM statistics) and GLOBIOM projections of soy harvested area (million hectares) in Brazil for 2000-2020, and GLOBIOM projections by 2050 for various SSPs. Values are differentiated by Brazilian federal state (colours) and soy cropping systems ('single-cropped' for single soy and 'multi-cropped' for soya-corn double cropping).

While harvested area trends can be quite comparable between GLOBIOM projections for some states, for some others the trends can diverge, in particular for 2020 for both single cropping

(e.g., Goiás GO, Minas Gerais MG) and double cropping (e.g., Mato Grosso MT, Mato Grosso do Sul MS, Parana PR). A dedicated effort is needed to adjust further the parameters controlling soy harvested area and production expansion across various subnational scale production units to match trends at the federal state level. To that end, additional sensitivity analysis on parameters controlling harvested area expansion in each federal state and cropping system, as well as yield improvements over 2000-2020, maybe conducted. Consistently with the results presented earlier, the projections of harvested areas by 2050 show an increase in harvested area at national scale but can vary across SSPs. The much lower area by 2050 in SSP1 as compared to SSP2 is localized in a few states (with however a larger harvested area in some states in SSP1 than in SSP2 – e.g., Para PA), which indicates the need to also pay attention to the parameters controlling soy harvested expansion at subnational scale in the context of future scenarios.

Biodiversity impacts in the world in and within Brazil

Figure 13 provides the projected land stress impacts on biodiversity a) from all managed land (i.e., annual and permanent cropland, pasture, forestry) in the same world regions as presented in previous figures (left, separating key countries for oilseed markets from the rest of the world ROW), and b) for annual crops only (including, but not only, soy) in the five major biomes of Brazil for (right). For a specific point in time, the occupation impacts represent the biodiversity loss of all managed land use (e.g., cropland, pasture and managed forests) in one year as compared to a situation in which that land was in a natural state, in fraction of global species loss. The occupation impacts therefore represent an allocation of the total loss of species to how the land is used at a given time step. The transformation impacts, on the other hand, represent the biodiversity impact of all land use changes (e.g., deforestation) in one year, accumulated over the time necessary for biodiversity recovery if that land use change was immediately reverted. The occupation impacts therefore informs on the temporally accumulated future impacts of current land use change, should it reverted right away. In a sense, at a given time step, the occupation impacts informs on total species loss over all managed land, while the transformation impacts informs on impacts of changes in how the land is managed.

Figure 13 - Projections of total occupation (bottom panels) and transformation (bottom panels) land stress impacts on biodiversity across a) selected GLOBIOM regions and b) Brazil federal state levels with the improved model version, from 2010 to 2050 for SSP2, and 2050 values for SSP1 and SSP3.

The projections of occupation impacts depict an increasing total biodiversity impact from managed land (as it expands) over both the 2000-2020 and the 2020-2050 periods, with a slight slowing down. Impacts in the key countries for oilseed markets are responsible about one third of global impacts in 2010, with Brazil being a hotspot of biodiversity loss. Except for SSP1 scenario, both the global impacts and the impacts in key countries for oilseed markets (including Brazil) increase over time, even though the share those countries represent in total impacts decline (i.e., impacts do not increase as fast as in the rest of the world). Even the decline in global impacts projected by 2050 as compared to 2020 does not guarantee a reversing of the global biodiversity loss, as this ignores the time lags associated with the underlying biodiversity gain, and the fact that biodiversity might never fully to natural state.

Within Brazil, in 2010 the occupation impacts from annual crops are primarily distributed in the Atlantic Forest biome (Mata Atlantica, slightly less than half of all impacts) and the Cerrado and Amazon biomes. These proportions remain relatively stable while total impacts increase both until 2020 and beyond, except for SSP1 (for which 2050 impacts seem comparable to 2020 impacts). Although a closer comparison to historical land use change would be useful, this is broadly consistent with historical land use patterns, that include large conversions from pasture to cropland in the Atlantic Forest biomes, as well as vegetation losses to agriculture in the Amazon, and a mix of the two in the Cerrado biome (Souza et al. 2020).

Comparatively to occupation impacts, transformation impacts in key countries for oilseed markets represent a greater share of global impacts in 2010 (i.e., close to half of global transformation impacts, instead of a third for occupation impacts), and therefore indicate a particularly high pressure on biodiversity in these countries. Both the total global transformation impacts and the share of it represented by key countries for oilseed markets decrease over time, with a larger (resp. lower) decline between 2020 and 2050 for SSP1 (resp. SSP3) than for SSP2. Although these results are only illustrative and some key policies (e.g., Forest Code, Soy Moratorium) are missing, at the level of Brazil biomes the transformation impacts from annual crops is less contrasted across all three future scenarios by 2050 (with an overall decrease). However, differentiated trends can occur across biomes between 2020 and 2050, highlighting potentially shifting pressures: e.g., transformation impacts for annual crops decrease continuously over the period in SSP2 for the Atlantic Forest biome, but increase over the 2020-2030 period for the Amazon and Cerrado.

Next to previously mentioned additional efforts to improve the dynamics of oilseed markets and land use in Brazil, the planned dedicated additional integration of methods presented in D6.3 (including the novel biodiversity data generated in WP2 and integrated in LCIA methods in WP6) will provide a richer picture of biodiversity impacts. More accurate estimates of impacts from land use on biodiversity will be achieved by using, next to the LC-IMPACT land stress characterization factors used in this deliverable, the novel land stress characterization factors generated in by CLEVER partners (see D6.3). Similarly, as done with GLOBIOM in D6.3, using characterization factors for other ecosystems (e.g., freshwater ecosystems) and forms of impacts (climate change, water stress, freshwater eutrophication) would provide a more complete picture of various channels of impacts.

Discussion

As demonstrated by the projections from the illustrative scenarios, the model improvements enabled a richer description of dynamics in soy markets globally, and soy production in Brazil:

- The detailed modelling of oilseed markets allows to better take interdependencies across vegetal oils and protein meals, and possible substitutions between individual oils and protein meals. The model improvements included the modelling of additional processes (crushing, substitutions between individual protein meals in feed and between individual oils for food and other uses) and products (individual oils and protein meals), and related demand projections and trade calibration. Some additional model improvements, like the increased use of protein meals in animal feed ration, were also important to reproduce historical trends in key variables such as the demand for soy imports to China. The illustrative projections are qualitatively and quantitatively aligned with observed trends over 2000-2020 and authoritative projections to 2030, and projections to 2050 confirmed the growing importance of soy and soy-based supply chains, in particular in relation to recent and future trends in livestock product consumption. The projections also illustrated interdependencies between feed and other end uses as a medium for propagation of changes in livestock demand to other oilseed market components, and anticipated future growth in biodiversity impacts from soy production regions like Brazil – unless the global demand for livestock products is moderated.
- At the same time, historical trends in the demand and trade of secondary products (cakes and oils), and the production and supply of primary crops were only partially aligned with observations. As part of future developments in CLEVER to improve the modelling of individual supply chain actors (task 6.5) and build scenarios (tasks 7.2 and 7.3), we will focus on improving the parameters to match historical trends in demand, supply and trade for key players for individual oilseed products, including Brazil, USA, Argentina, EU and China for soy supply chains. We will also include a parameterization of key international policies, such as the EU-MERCOSUR free trade agreement and the EUDR imported deforestation control policy. This will rely on a modification of various trade cost components, such as tariffs, quotas, and additional trade costs, as informed by a combination the econometric work conducted in task 3.2 (see deliverable D3.2) to estimate the impact of such interventions on physical trade flows, and a sensitivity analysis with GLOBIOM to identify the range of parameter changes required to achieve a similar outcome.
- The improved model also demonstrated its capacity to capture the dynamics of soy production at subnational level in Brazil, including intensification options such as the development of multicropping, and differences across regions and biomes in resulting biodiversity impacts. This is a key factor for accurately representing the dynamic link between international soy supply chains, related governance interventions and impacts on natural resources, such as land use change and biodiversity loss. The analysis of illustrative projections showed some margin for improvement in calibrating the subnational level developments of various soy production systems in Brazil to match historical trends. As part of future developments in CLEVER to improve the modelling of individual supply chain actors (task 6.5) and build scenarios (tasks 7.2 and 7.3), we will adjust further some of the parameters controlling harvested area and production

expansion at subnational level, as well additional modelling features from the Brazil-zoomed version of GLOBIOM co-developed with INPE, such as the revised Forest Code (Soterroni et al 2018) or the Soy moratorium (Soterroni et al 2019). Similarly, while we build further on the biodiversity impact methods developed in Task 6.3, and will use in Brazil the refined biodiversity characterization factors generated by CLEVER partners.

- Additional features may also be useful to the scenario analysis foreseen in WP7. For example, a more detailed footprinting module, linking land use change and biodiversity loss in producing regions to not only production activities in Brazil but also their final destination (e.g., meat consumption in Europe), could be developed. This effort could also make use of the TRASE dataset (linking soy production at municipality level to various traders and destination markets) and empirical evidence generated in WP3 on the stickiness of subnational supply chains. Similar to other supply chains, the upcoming stakeholder workshop might also provide additional suggestions and priorities for further model improvements.

Forest supply chains

Results from illustrative projections

Forest area and management in BASE scenario before and after model improvements

After the implementation of the model developments described in the methods section, we can observe under the improved version that there is an increase of the total land cover in the model globally of 569 Mha in year 2020, due to calibration to the new forest area data which shifted the total forest area also in year 2000 (FRA 2020) (Figure 14). The main difference within the land cover classes is that the unmanaged forests in the new version are about 1800 Mha less than the unmanaged area in the standard version, due to a higher share of managed forests (more extensively managed). The later amounts to 2200 Mha in year 2020 in the CLEVER version.

The new land cover includes also the dynamics due to afforestation/deforestation, where the afforestation contributes to increasing forest area in the order of 121 Mha by 2020. However, at the same time there is also 239 Mha decrease due to deforestation sourced from new FRA (2020) and G4M data. In the long term, afforestation is expected to increase and reach 820 Mha by 2100, whereas deforestation remains rather stable in the long run (at the level of year 2020). It can be observed that plantation area in the new version of the model is divided between forest plantations and energy plantations, while in the previous version there were no plantations within forest areas. Additionally, there is a less pronounced expansion of energy plantations, reaching 195 Mha by 2100 in the new version compared to 418 Mha in the status quo.

Figure 14 - Development of global land cover according to land use classes before and after the model improvements for this CLEVER deliverable (BASE scenario).

In this improved version, the forest area reaches about 400 Mha more than the status quo version in year 2020 (calibration to FRA2020) and about 1000 Mha higher by 2100. The managed forests are divided according to different management classes in the new version and the sum of the forest area obtained as sum of Medium intensity, High intensity and Forest Plantations is not increasing over time in the new formulation, whereas there was a significant expansion of managed forests in the status-quo formulation. This stable overall production area is due to management intensification between/within different management classes rather than by expanding the managed forest area as it was observed in the status-quo version (Figure 15).

Figure 15 - Development of global forest area of various management classes before and after the improvements in the model for this CLEVER deliverable (BASE scenario).

Forest management area projections across scenarios

The global forest area in 2020 is 4.05 Billion ha. Under the BASE scenario, forest area increases by 253 Mha by 2050, due to an increase over time of afforestation and the stabilization of deforestation over time. Under the BASE scenario, in absence of future plantation expansion, given the increasing wood demands, there is a conversion of secondary forests to managed forest for 34 Mha and at the same time an intensification from medium intensity to high intensity management for 56 Mha, these two effects together are able satisfy the increase in wood demands (Figure 16).

Forest plantations expansion in new areas is observed to increase global forest area under the FORPLANT and AGPLANT by 18 Mha and 105 Mha respectively in 2050 when compared to BASE. In all scenarios, the global area of plantations remains at a relatively low share of the total forest area, generally not exceeding 5% of the total forest area by 2050. The FORPLANT scenario, even if leading to the largest area of forest plantations being established (239 Mha) by 2050, if compared to AGPLANT (212 Mha), there is only a marginal expansion of forest area, given that the expansion of plantations area is driven by an intensification from the medium and high intensity management classes compared to BASE. Despite forest plantation expansion in FORPLANT happens only within forest area, total forest area increases also under this scenario compared to BASE, given the increase of competitiveness of forest land compared to agriculture, which leads to an overall reduction of deforestation compared to BASE. A less pronounced

intensification within forest area is observed in the AGPLANT scenario where plantations are expanded outside forest area. However, in both scenarios there is also a release of secondary forests compared to BASE, with a secondary forest area exceeding BASE by 148 Mha under FORPLANT and 231 Mha under AGPLANT.

Figure 16 - Development of global forest area under various forest management classes (including expansion of plantations within and outside forest land) for the different scenarios, with the improved model version.

If considering the expansion of the plantation area according to global regions, we can observe that most of the new plantation area expansion is expected to take place in Asia, Africa and Latin America (Figure 17). These regions together represent currently 83% of the global plantation area. By 2050 they will represent 90-91% of the plantation area depending on scenario (FORPLANT, AGPLANT), given that the other regions keep almost constant their plantations areas over time.

Figure 17 - Development of global forest plantation area, detailed by aggregated regions (with the improved model version).

In Latin America, under the FORPLANT, we observe the maximum expansion of plantations (75 Mha). In this scenario, plantations expand within forest area mostly by reducing the area managed with medium and high intensity. Under the AGPLANT scenario, plantations area reaches 55 Mha, of which 35 Mha are established in agricultural land.

Figure 18 - Development of forest area under to forest management classes for the different scenarios in the Latin America aggregated region (with the improved model version).

Roundwood harvest volume projections across scenarios

Under the BASE scenario, global roundwood harvest is expected to increase from 3.9 billion m³ to 4.3 billion m³ by 2050 (a 10% increase) (Figure 19). Under BASE, the share of roundwood from plantations is 34% in 2020 and 33% in 2050 (one third of global roundwood harvest), given that the area is not expanding over time. Under the FORPLANT, total timber harvest exceeds the BASE development by 144 Mm³ in 2050, with the share of roundwood harvested from plantations reaching 62% of the total harvest. Under the AGPLANT, total roundwood harvest exceeds the BASE by 109 Mm³ in 2050 and the roundwood share from plantations reaches 55% of the total harvest.

Figure 19 - Development of global forest harvest volume under managed forests vs plantations in the different scenarios (with the improved model version).

The trend in roundwood harvest across regions shows in the BASE scenario (if comparing 2050 and 2020 regional levels), there will be a significant increase in Latin America (+25%) and Asia (+12), a minor increase in Africa (+6%) and EU (+5%) and stable harvest in Former Soviet Union (0%) and US (-1) (Figure 20). The expansion of plantations under FORPLANT/AGPLANT amplifies the increase of harvest in Latin America (+38%/+34%) and Asia (+19%/+18%) and reduces further the harvest in the US (-9%/-8%) with minor effects in the other regions.

Figure 20 - Development of harvest volumes, detailed by aggregated regions (with the improved model version).

Trade volume projections across scenarios

Net export of harvested wood products (as aggregate of primary and secondary wood products) under the BASE scenario shows that Latin America and Asia could become more competitive in the future and North America could reduce its competitiveness, with the other regions showing stable trends (Figure 21). The future trends under the scenarios reflects closely the trends observed for roundwood harvest. The scenarios where expansion of plantations take places (FORPLANT/AGPLANT) further promotes net export from Latin America and Asia. Hence, these two regions become more competitive in their export also because they are harvesting more roundwood than the other regions from plantations. Under the same scenarios, there is a complementary net export reduction in North America compared to BASE. The net trade in the other regions appears to be less sensitive to the different scenarios and more stable over time.

Figure 21 - Net export (i.e., export minus import) of primary and semifinished wood products, for six aggregated regions (with the improved model version).

Land use biodiversity impact projections across scenarios

The early results are presented for one of the biodiversity indicators coupled to the land use scenarios, that measures the as the Potential Disappeared Fraction of global species aggregated over all different taxa (PDF %). When comparing 2020 and 2050, the global biodiversity impacts from all land uses under the BASE scenario are decreasing over time, driven overall by a substantial reduction in grassland areas (Figure 22), triggered by the reduction in animal product consumption after the application of a carbon tax on related GHG emissions. An expansion of energy crops impacts is visible, but lower than the reduction of the grassland impacts.

Under the FORPLANT scenario, the expansion of forest plantations within the forest area leads to an overall global increase of impacts, given the replacement of other less intensive forest

management classes. Hence, impacts under FORPLANT 2050 are lower than in 2020 but exceeds the ones under BASE 2050.

Under the AGLPLANT 2050 scenario, the overall impacts are comparable to the ones observed under BASE 2050. However, there is a substantial difference in the composition of impacts compared to BASE. Under AGLPLANT we observe a contraction of impacts from natural and seminatural forest managements and the expansion of impacts from forest plantations located outside forest land (on former cropland and grassland). The expansion of plantations in agricultural land does not diminish significantly impacts from cropland and grassland, the reason is that there is a plantation-induced displacement of agricultural land on non-forest natural vegetation areas (a reference land category for biodiversity richness). This type of knock-on effect from plantations highlight risks of displacing the pressure from forests to other natural ecosystems. The modelled related biodiversity impacts might however be exaggerated: the impact of such conversion assumed that all of the lost other natural vegetation consist of old secondary or even primary other natural vegetation, while some of it might be recently abandoned agricultural land, for which conversion back to agricultural land might be less detrimental to biodiversity. Better accounting for this requires keeping track of abandoned agricultural land as a separate land pool, and modelling both its conversion to agricultural land or forest plantations, and the time dynamics of biodiversity recovery after abandonment.

Figure 22 - Global land use biodiversity impacts measured by the Potential Disappeared Fraction of global species (%) (with the new model version).

In Latin America, the biodiversity impacts of the alternative plantation's scenarios are pronounced compared to BASE (Figure 23). In particular, the FORPLANT scenario increases

impacts by 0.7% PDF compared to BASE, given the replacement of less intensive forest managements in natural and seminatural forests by the establishment of plantations. The AGPLANT allows to reduce the impacts from forest management by release of natural and seminatural forests, however, it increases the leakage of land to other natural vegetation (see above for global impacts), and overall leads to a slight increase (0.2% PDF) of biodiversity loss compared to BASE.

Figure 23 - Latin America biodiversity impacts measured by the Potential Disappeared Fraction of global species (%) (with the new model version).

Discussion

The developments in the improved version of GLOBIOM for this deliverable have significantly enhanced its capacity to simulate forest sector dynamics, offering a more nuanced understanding of land use and forest management impacts:

- The model improvements in the representation of forest management have demonstrated the importance of management intensity shifts in meeting rising wood demands without significantly expanding the forest area under management, that as a consequence leads to saving of forests that can be restored to natural conditions.
- Including in the model the possibility to expand plantations for roundwood production outside forest land has demonstrated an alternative to further release pressure on natural forest resources by expanding wood production to other land uses and creating new forest area, with however risks to displacing the pressure on other natural land.
- The model's ability to simulate wood products trade dynamics highlighted the growing importance of certain global regions, in particular Latin America and Asia. These are global regions that will most benefit from expansion of forest plantation areas in terms of wood trade competitiveness but also preservation of natural forest areas.

To enable a better modeling of the foreseen model and scenario analysis in CLEVER, a few additional improvements may be considered in the frame additional modeling improvements for the CLEVER deliverable D6.5:

- The risk of indirect land-use changes, for example non-forest natural vegetation indirect land conversion following the conversion of agricultural land to plantations, and potential biodiversity impacts. This would require an explicit modeling of abandoned land and the time dynamics of biodiversity recovery in it.
- It would be relevant to include the synergies and tradeoff between biodiversity and the carbon dynamics. To this aim, the model would need to include explicitly age structures dynamics calibrated according to the forest management classes. A global dataset for calibration of age structures is available from (Besnard et al. 2021) and can be mobilized.
- It would also be important to improve the calibration of historical forest and land uses dynamics at the regional level, particularly for Brazil, and potentially include the effect of key policies such as the Forest Code. Incorporating local data sources will ensure that the model better reflects real-world dynamics. To this aim, local datasets like the MapBiomass have been identified. Complementary, modeling improvements specific for Brazil undertaken for the Soy supply chains (described in this deliverable) could be integrated with the forest sector modeling improvements.
- Future developments should also explore scenarios that explicitly link plantation expansion to restoration goals. This could involve evaluating how plantations can restore degraded lands or contribute to local conservation targets in Brazil, while avoiding the conversion of natural forests. Such scenarios will enhance the model's capacity to guide national sustainable land-use strategies.
- The integration of the SSP2-RCP1.9 scenarios has provided valuable insights into the interaction of socioeconomic growth and high mitigation ambition effects on forest management in a situation of high wood demand. Expanding the set of scenarios by including higher levels of wood demands will further enable the exploration of a broader range of impacts and provide more robust results.

Aquaculture and aquafeed supply chains

Results from illustrative projections

Demand for final blue food products

As shown in Figure 24, in the BAU scenario the global demand for fish final products remains relatively stable or slightly increases (i.e., less than +15%) between 2020 and 2050 for most products, with a few exceptions. On the one hand, some products are projected to undergo a more significant increase in global demand, for example freshwater (FRSH, +32%) and shrimps & prawns (SHRI, +23%). This is compatible with projections from others (e.g., Naylor et al 2021), with countries from Eastern Asia (EAS, including China) remaining largest consumers of freshwater and crustacean products but with a more moderate increase than recent decades, but also countries from South (SAS, e.g., India) and South-East Asia (SEA) seeing a large relative increase by 2050. On the other hand, some other products, are expected to decrease substantially, notably fish meal and fish oil. For example, fish oil is expected to decrease from about 0.8 Mt in 2020 to about 0.2 Mt in 2050, representing about a 75% decrease. This follows the assumed prolongation of recent trends in fed aquaculture in terms of feed conversion efficiency gains and substitution of fish meal and fish oil feed by crop-based feed. Trends can be more variable at regional level, with for example marked decreases in molluscs (MLSC) and cephalopods (CEPH) in South Asia (SAS). Most of the trends in final products are related to food use and to some extent other uses, with the exception of fish meal and fish oil, used for feed.

Figure 24 - Projections of demand of blue food final products for food, feed and other use (i.e., excluding input to reduction sector) by product, aggregated to ten world regions.

Assumptions from the AF20 scenario does not affect the final demand for food and other use most products by 2050. The effect however considerable for fishmeal and fish oil products, with projected 2050 values larger than 2020 values, thereby reversing recent trends in the total consumption of fishmeal and fish oil.

Primary blue food product supply and aquafeed use

Figure 25 a) shows the projected supply of primary fish products, distinguished by source (between catch, fed and non-fed aquaculture). It should first be noted that total supply for primary fish products is considerably larger than the demand of final product for food, feed and other use, due to losses in processing stages (e.g., processing and reduction sector). For example, in the BAU scenario by 2020, the supply primary product across all species groups is about 176 Mt at global scale, while the demand of final product is about 86 Mt. Since wild catch and non-fed aquaculture capacities are assumed respectively constant to 2020 levels and highly constrained in the BAU scenario after 2020, by assumption all the supply increase is projected to be sourced from fed aquaculture. In the BAU scenario, the total supply of primary blue food products is expected to continue increasing, with a somewhat reduced speed as compared to recent past: it increases from about 176 Mt to about 192 Mt by 2030 and to 214 Mt by 2050. This translates into a +48% increase in fed aquaculture supply, from 80 Mt in 2020 to about 106 Mt in 2050. These projections are qualitatively comparable to those from the OECD-FAO Outlook 2024-2033 (OECD-FAO 2024).

Figure 25 - Projections at global scale of a) total blue food primary products supply by source and b) crop-based aquafeed used by crop.

As previously discussed, due to further feed conversion efficiency improvements and replacement of fishmeal and fish oil by crop-based aquafeed, the amount of fishmeal and fish oil used for feed reduces. Meanwhile, as illustrated in Figure 25 b), the amount of crop-based aquafeed increases from about 79 Mt in 2020 to about 106 Mt in 2050. This represents a +34% increase over the period, which is slightly lower than the growth in aquafeed: despite the

assumed further substitution of fishmeal and fish oil by crop-based aquafeed, the assumed further increase in feed conversion efficiency buffer the future increase in the demand for aquafeed. By assumption, the proportion of various crops in total crop-based aquafeed differs across regions but remains constant over the different time horizons and scenarios. Corn dominates other crops in large parts of Asia, Latin America and Sub-Saharan Africa, and globally represents about two third of crop total crop aquafeed. Wheat dominates in a few regions (Europe, Former Soviet Union, Oceania and to some extent Northern America) and has globally a slightly higher share in total crop-based aquafeed than soya, which is the second most used crop for aquafeed in large parts of the world. Rapeseed provides a minor contribution to aquafeed in a few regions like Europe and Northern America, negligible at global scale.

As noted previously, assuming that the post-2020 increases in feed conversion efficiency and changes to the composition of aquafeed assumed in the BAU scenario do not take place (AF20 scenario) leads to a reversal of the decrease in fish meal and fish oil supply. As illustrated in Figure 25, this leads to slightly higher increase in crop-based aquafeeds by 2050 (+48% increase over 2020-2050, instead of +34% in the BAU scenario), fully matching the relative change in fed aquaculture in the BAU scenario. There is no visible impact on total blue food primary supply, which can be explained by two factors that moderates the impact of post-2020 fishmeal and fish oil. First, by 2020 the share crop-based aquafeed has already increased as compared to the year 2000, and so did the feed conversion efficiency, leading to lower fish-based feed requirements per unit of output from fed aquaculture. In addition, in line with OECD-FAO Outlook, the share of fishmeal and fish oil sourced from fish processing waste (rather than primary fish) also decreased over 2000-2020 and is assumed to increase even further by further by 2030, to further reductions in the primary fish required to generate one unit of fish-based aquafeed.

Land use and biodiversity impacts associated with crop aquafeed requirements

As shown in Figure 26 a), the crop used as aquafeed represents a moderate share of total global production projected by 2050 for each crop: up to 3% for Wheat, 5% for Corn and 6% for Soya. This share does not increase after 2020 in the BAU scenario but increases slightly in the AF20 scenario, implying that the demands from aquaculture does not increase faster than that of other demands, unless feed conversion efficiency does not increase – and even so, the relative share of aquafeed increases only marginally. As displayed in Figure 26 b), the overall demand for agricultural products drives an expansion of agricultural land covers (cropland and grassland) from 2020 to 2050 of about 300 million hectares (bring total agricultural area expansion as compared to 2000 to about 500 million hectares), at the expense of forest and – in larger proportion – other natural vegetation.

Figure 26 - Projections at global scale of a) the share crop aquafeed represents in total crop supply (%) and b) the net difference to crop-based aquafeed used by crop.

With the uptake of the biodiversity impact quantification developed in the CLEVER deliverable D6.3, it is possible to estimate the biodiversity impacts from the crop-based aquafeed through land use change (see methods). However, the pathway from demand to final land use impact in the agricultural system can be mediated by several factors such as intensification dynamics and trade, which do not respond linearly. It is therefore challenge to isolate the land use from the additional demand from crop aquafeed, and the average impact of 1 ton of demand from the same region where the demand originates might be a very limited proxy. One modelling approach to such an issue is to look at differences across scenarios with varying levels of demand for crop aquafeed, such as BAU and AF20 scenarios.

Figure 27 provides the difference between the BAU and AF20 scenarios after 2020 for key variables, and helps illustrate the complexities in the transmission of impacts from the crop aquafeed demand to biodiversity impacts. It suggests that the BAU scenario projects savings of crop aquafeed demand by about 1.5, 6 and 10 Mt by 2030, 2040 and 2050, primarily in Eastern Asia (ESA), and to some extent in South Asia (SAS) and South East Asia (SEA). However, as suggested by the middle panel, due to the trade dependencies of these regions, land use intensification and other market knock-on effects, the related natural land savings occur primarily in Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC), with smaller impacts in the regions of original demand, that sometimes vary in sign across time horizons. The final biodiversity impacts, however, shows an even more complicated picture, with avoided biodiversity loss in LAC (consistently with land savings in this biodiverse part of the world) that however do not reflect the temporal trend in land saving. Biodiversity savings also occur in regions where crop aquafeed demand with much higher biodiversity gains in proportion to land savings (e.g., SEA).

Figure 27 - Net difference between the BAU and AF20 scenarios after 2020, in crop aquafeed use (left panel, million tons), extent of natural land cover (middle panel, million hectares) and total extinction risks impact on terrestrial ecosystems (right panel, potentially disappeared fraction). The stacked bars of different colours indicates the different world regions aggregated from original GLOBIOM regions.

Nitrogen losses from finfish aquaculture activities

As shown in Figure 28 for finfish aquaculture, the projected increase in fed freshwater aquaculture production is expected to generate additional reactive nitrogen losses through on-site waste (excretion by fish). Total on-site N waste in finfish aquaculture is expected to grow from 0.24 million tons of nitrogen (MtN) in 2020, to about 0.32 MtN by 2050 for the BAU scenario (i.e., +31% over 2020-2050), or about 0.37 MtN (i.e., +54% over 2020-2050). Overall, by comparing the AF20 and BAU scenario by 2050, it seems that the combined effect of further increased feed conversion efficiency and increased share of crops in aquafeed assumed in the BAU scenario leads to saving modest savings in N waste.

Figure 28 - Projected nitrogen losses in finfish aquaculture at global scale.

Discussion

The illustrative projections highlights the capacities of the improved GLOBIOM-Fish model to explore various future scenarios concerning blue food demand trends, the contribution of aquaculture to meeting future blue food demands, the impact of future technological progress in the reduction sector and aquaculture feeding practices on pressures on water systems (in terms of catch levels for fish-based aquafeeds and nutrient losses to water steams) and terrestrial ecosystems (in terms of land use change via crop-based aquafeeds and extinction risks for terrestrial ecosystems) on biodiversity.

- The projections of final demand for food and other use, as well as aquaculture-related feed, at the level of species-group level allow a nuance representation of future changes in blue food demand. Our projections a business-level scenario for population and dietary preferences projects a slowed but prolonged increase in blue food product demand, in particular for freshwater species-based products, consistently with other studies. Following the expressed interest of stakeholders in a dedicated stakeholder workshop, it might be of interest to explore an alternative demand scenario focused on a shift of consumer preferences away from historical trends, towards low trophic level-species (e.g., farmed bivalves, seaweed) with higher levels of environmental sustainability (Gephart et al. 2021; Slater and James 2023).
- The representation of various aquaculture systems and their fish-based and crop-based requirements, as well as the processing and reduction sector allows to capture important recent technical trends in supply-chain processes that accompanied the evolution of aquaculture practices and the aquafeed supply, such as changes in feed conversion efficiency, substitutions between fish-based and crop-based aquafeeds, and an higher recycling of fish processing losses into fishmeal and fish oil production. Projections for our illustrative scenarios, contrasting a prolongation of feed conversion efficiency gains and fish-based aquafeed substitution with an alternative scenario excluding those, illustrate the model capacity to account for alternative futures. Some parameters may be further refined when developing further the scenarios (e.g., maximum levels of fish oil substitution rate). Based on the interest expressed by stakeholders, a scenario picturing more efficient, integrated aquaculture systems (Valenti and Ballester 2024), coupled with the alternative demand scenario picturing low trophic species could be of interest. The required efforts to parameterize such a scenario might however be beyond the scope of the CLEVER project, but perhaps a scenario looking into the substitution of crop-based aquafeeds by macro-algae could be explored, following the example of similar scenarios for substituting crops by macro-algae for land-based biomass use for food, feed and biofuel with GLOBIOM model (Spillias et al. 2023). Another possible direction for the scenarios would be to explore what the implications of sustainable catch levels would be for the rest of the blue food supply chains. This would however require acquiring data on such sustainable levels for the various species groups and regions considered in the GLOBIOM-Fish model.
- The connection of the blue food supply chain representation to the agricultural supply chains allows to explore the impacts of the crop-based aquafeed requirements on the agricultural markets and related impacts on the land resources and biodiversity. Our illustrative projections allow to integrate crop-based aquafeed demand into with other demands for food, feed and other use, and highlight that even if increasing the crop-

based aquafeed requirements remain a small share of total crop production. The improved CLEVER model connects the detailed modelling of agricultural markets and resource use (including trade, demand, land use intensity and land use change adjustments) and related biodiversity impacts (including the importance of the spatial location of agricultural production activities, and the uptake of model developments undertaken in CLEVER task 6.3), and dedicated scenario comparison methods can be used to isolate the specific impact of aquaculture feed demand amid other changes in agricultural markets and resource use from 2020 to 2050. We for example show that biodiversity Latin America may be particularly exposed to future demand for crop-based aquafeed in other regions, and that spatial patterns of biodiversity may be important factors mediating the link between land use changes and biodiversity impacts. To improve the understanding of the various scenarios considered, an additional reference scenario, similar to our AF20 scenario but also featuring a level of demand for final blue food products constant to 2020 levels could be useful to better isolate the role of demand-side assumptions. Similarly, it might be relevant to explore the impact of uncertainties in key modelling assumptions, such as the share of various crops in total crop-based aquafeed requirements.

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